

OPERAS

open scholarly communication in the european
research area for social sciences and humanities

Annual Report 2024

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Foreword / Wstep

2024

ENGLISH

2024 Looking back on 2024, we see the increasing importance of Open Science for research and society. Against a backdrop of intricate global and political dynamics, we have navigated the intertwined challenges posed by the rapid advancements in artificial intelligence, the proliferation of disinformation, and critical questions surrounding data ownership and technological sovereignty. **OPERAS, as the European Research Infrastructure dedicated to open scholarly communication for the social sciences and humanities, continues to position itself at the forefront of these challenges, as a trusted and reliable voice when trust is more fragile than ever.**

Over the past year, OPERAS has diligently strengthened its work across core mission areas while strategically navigating these complex headwinds.

OPERAS draws its strength from the extensive and varied community. In recognition of this foundational attribute, we are initiating a new tradition with this annual report: representatives of our National Nodes will henceforth provide the forewords. This initiative presents a valuable opportunity to highlight the notable achievements of a specific node within the reporting year. Furthermore, to underscore OPERAS's steadfast commitment to multilingualism, we present this introduction in two languages, reflecting the rich linguistic diversity of our network.

During 2024, the Polish National Node led by IBL PAN made notable advancements, successfully concluding a comprehensive two-year preparatory project dedicated to engaging with the scholarly community and assessing its requirements. This foundational work culminated in the formal establishment of the OPERAS-PL consortium, which subsequently submitted a bid for inclusion on the national roadmap of research infrastructures. **Another important outcome of these endeavours was the publication of an Open Humanities Manifesto.** Over 200 individuals and 15 institutions endorsed this document, which advocates for a transformative shift within Polish humanities towards open science, stressing the imperative for new evaluation frameworks that acknowledge diverse research outputs and foster open publishing paradigms.

This year's Polish contributions to OPERAS have also resonated at the European level. Notably, the Polish node has spearheaded the development of the OPERAS Innovation Lab and actively participated in numerous European projects designed to enhance OPERAS services and realise its overarching objectives. The recent addition of two new OPERAS members from Poland —the Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center and the University of Silesia in Katowice—further evidences the expansion and increasing maturity of the Polish node. These developments collectively illustrate the Polish node's substantial growth and its unwavering commitment to progressing OPERAS's mission and assuming a prominent role within its vibrant scholarly community.

Apart from the foreword, readers will also notice the overall structural evolution of the Annual Report. This year, it is organised around the objectives outlined in our Strategic Plan, directly connecting our activities with the goals we have set for ourselves. This new structure will provide clearer insight into the impact and direction of our collective efforts. This foreword, however, contextualises the work undertaken last year within the overarching framework of OPERAS' strategic pillars.

The "*Redesigning Ecosystem*" pillar has been significantly advanced through the establishment of robust governance and legal frameworks for the future formulation of ERIC. The continued growth and dynamism of our National Nodes has supported this process. Their activities — from building new services and infrastructures to leading meaningful national discussions — have been vital in expanding OPERAS' reach and deepening our impact across Europe. **Our National Nodes serve as critical bridges between national and European levels, forming essential pillars in the construction of a more interconnected and sustainable research infrastructure.** OPERAS further strengthened this ecosystem by actively confronting the global disinformation crisis, organising events like TrustOn2024 and

contributing to the UN General Assembly. These actions reaffirm our commitment to integrity, transparency, and the protection of spaces where knowledge can thrive free from manipulation within this redesigned scholarly communication landscape.

The "*Empowering Community*" pillar was reinforced by targeted engagement, outreach, and training activities for users, researchers and society. Pursuing this goal, the OPERAS Innovation Lab significantly advanced its objective of guiding authors and stakeholders in adopting innovative SSH scholarly outputs. It established its dual approach as an Observatory—conducting case studies and generating recommendations for innovators—and an Accelerator—offering concrete support such as consulting, training, and funding guidance. Through its updated website and blog, the Lab established itself as a vital knowledge hub for the SSH community.

The "*Supporting Bibliodiversity*" pillar remains a core focus, with key endeavours like DIAMAS mapping the diverse Diamond OA landscape, or PALOMERA surveying the Open Access policies for monographs in ERA. A particular highlight this year has been the substantial progress of the Diamond Open Access model. Across our member countries, we have witnessed necessary steps toward strengthening national ecosystems, building national consortia, and solidifying commitments to sustainable, community-driven publishing models. These efforts are not only crucial for scholarly communities but also serve as a broader statement about the values of openness, collaboration, and resilience in times of uncertainty.

Finally, the "*Fostering Quality*" pillar is addressed by building standard risk management frameworks and ensuring consistent quality in project outcomes. In 2024, OPERAS made substantial progress in the field of services by bringing three new services into full production (VERA, Metrics and OPERAS-ID). This demonstrates yet another step towards providing stable, well-defined, and fully operational services that enhance the overall quality and accessibility of SSH scholarship.

It is worth noting that work on each of those pillars was carried out in numerous international projects. This demonstrates not only a vibrant community behind OPERAS, ready to prepare, lead, and contribute to collaborative endeavours, but also targeted infrastructure growth that encompasses diverse activities while remaining on track with the RI's key strategic pathways. Looking ahead, OPERAS secured further development along these strategic pathways through successful new funding bids, embedding AI and knowledge graphs in its services, as well as providing interdisciplinary expertise and more substantial support for the Diamond OA model. You will hear more about those achievements in next year's report.

Thus OPERAS further solidifies its role as a research infrastructure meaningful for its key communities. It serves as a vessel for its members and national nodes to advance important agendas and jointly deliver key services for their communities. It empowers researchers with services, support and knowledge to improve scholarly communication in SSH. It provides policymakers and funders with insights that support informed decision-making. It offers various organisations, initiatives and topical infrastructures in SSH with a transversal and interdisciplinary skillset practical for coordinating their scholarly communication endeavours. Finally, it serves society as a sustainable infrastructure supporting public debate, democracy, and freedom, not only through the transfer of knowledge but also by embodying high values of commitment and collaboration at a global scale.

To put it simply, OPERAS is where it's needed the most to tackle key challenges of scholarly communication, open science and society. Every year, we are solidifying the RI's impact on those key areas thanks to the strong, international and growing community.

Dr Maciej Maryl

OPERAS Executive Assembly Member, OPERAS-PL Coordinator, Director of Digital Humanities Centre at IBL PAN

2024

POLSKI

2024 Spoglądając na miniony rok, widzimy rosnące znaczenie otwartej nauki dla badań naukowych i społeczeństwa. W obliczu dynamicznych przemian geopolitycznych stawialiśmy czoła splatającym się wyzwaniom, wynikającym z gwałtownego postępu sztucznej inteligencji, szerzenia się dezinformacji oraz zagadnień własności danych i suwerenności technologicznej. OPERAS, jako europejska infrastruktura badawcza dla otwartej komunikacji naukowej w obszarze nauk społecznych i humanistycznych, konsekwentnie stawia czoła tym wyzwaniom, służąc jako zaufany i wiarygodny głos w czasach, gdy zaufanie stało się dobrem niezwykle rzadkim. W minionym roku OPERAS systematycznie umacniał swoje działania w kluczowych obszarach swojej misji.

OPERAS czerpie swoją siłę z rozległej i zróżnicowanej społeczności. Doceniając tę fundamentalną cechę, wraz z niniejszym raportem rocznym inicjujemy nową tradycję – odtąd autorami kolejnych wstępów będą przedstawiciele naszych Węzłów Krajowych (National Nodes). Dzięki temu zapewnimy im sposobność do uwypuklenia znaczących osiągnięć konkretnego węzła w danym roku sprawozdawczym. Co więcej, aby podkreślić zaangażowanie OPERAS w promowanie wielojęzyczności, prezentujemy niniejszy wstęp w dwóch językach, co odzwierciedla bogactwo językowe naszej sieci.

W 2024 roku polski Węzeł Krajowy, koordynowany przez Instytut Badań Literackich PAN, zakończył z powodzeniem kompleksowy dwuletni projekt przygotowawczy, którego celem było budowanie sieci współpracy i rozpoznanie potrzeb krajowego środowiska naukowego. W wyniku tych działań powstało konsorcjum OPERAS-PL, które ubiega się o wpis na Polską Mapę Infrastruktury Badawczej. Ważnym efektem tej inicjatywy była również publikacja [Manifestu Otwartej Humanistyki](#), podpisanego przez ponad 200 osób i 15 instytucji. Dokument ten wzywa do głębokich zmian w polskiej humanistyce w duchu otwartej nauki, w tym wypracowania nowych zasad ewaluacji, uwzględniających różnorodne wyniki badań i wspierających otwarte modele publikowania.

Tegoroczny wkład Polski w działania OPERAS jest też widoczny na poziomie europejskim. Polski węzeł kieruje rozwojem Laboratorium Innowacji (Innovation Lab) OPERAS oraz aktywnie uczestniczy w licznych projektach europejskich, mających na celu doskonalenie usług OPERAS i realizację jego celów strategicznych. Niedawne przystąpienie do OPERAS dwóch nowych członków z Polski – Poznańskiego Centrum Superkomputerowo-Sieciowego oraz Uniwersytetu Śląskiego w Katowicach – dodatkowo potwierdza rozwój i rosnącą dojrzałość polskiego węzła. Wszystkie te dokonania obrazują dynamiczny rozwój OPERAS-PL, jego wkład w realizację misji OPERAS i gotowość do odegrania znaczącej roli w tej infrastrukturze badawczej.

Oprócz nowego formatu wstępu, czytelnicy i czytelniczki dostrzegą również ogólną ewolucję struktury Raportu Roczno. W tym roku podporządkowaliśmy jego układ celom zarysowanym w Planie Strategicznym OPERAS, by bezpośrednio powiązać poszczególne działania z wytyczonymi kierunkami. Ta nowa forma prezentacji zapewnia lepszy wgląd w efekty naszych wspólnych wysiłków. Niniejszy wstęp natomiast sytuuje ubiegłoroczne działania podjęte w szerokim kontekście filarów strategicznych OPERAS.

W ramach filaru „Transformacja ekosystemu” przygotowano solidne ramy prawne i schemat zarządczy z myślą o przyszłym przekształceniu OPERAS w rozproszoną infrastrukturę badawczą o statusie ERIC. W procesie tym aktywnie uczestniczyły nasze Węzły Krajowe. Ich aktywność – od tworzenia nowych usług i infrastruktury po inicjowanie ważnych debat na szczeblu krajowym – miała kluczowe znaczenie dla zwiększenia zasięgu OPERAS i pogłębiania naszego oddziaływania w całej Europie. Nasze Węzły pełnią rolę łączników między poziomem krajowym a europejskim, stanowiąc podwaliny zintegrowanej i trwałej infrastruktury badawczej. OPERAS dodatkowo wzmacniał ekosystem komunikacji naukowej w kontekście globalnego kryzysu dezinformacyjnego, organizując wydarzenia takie jak TrustOn2024 oraz angażując się w prace Zgromadzenia Ogólnego ONZ. Działania te potwierdzają nasze przywiązanie do zasad uczciwości i przejrzystości, które realizujemy, tworząc przestrzeń komunikacji naukowej opartą na zaufaniu — taką, w której wiedza może swobodnie się rozwijać, wolna od manipulacji.

Filar „Wspieranie społeczności” został wzmocniony poprzez ukierunkowane działania angażujące, informacyjne i szkoleniowe, skierowane do użytkowników, badaczy i ogółu społeczeństwa. Laboratorium Innowacji OPERAS

poczyniło znaczne postępy w przygotowaniu oferty wsparcia we wdrażaniu nowatorskich form publikacji naukowych w naukach humanistycznych i społecznych. Laboratorium działa dwutorowo — jako Obserwatorium, które prowadzi badania i opracowuje rekomendacje dla innowatorów, oraz jako Akcelerator, oferujący konkretne wsparcie, takie jak konsultacje, szkolenia i doradztwo w zakresie finansowania prototypów nowych usług. Dzięki odświeżonej stronie internetowej i aktywnemu blogowi, Laboratorium stało się ważnym ośrodkiem wiedzy i inspiracji dla społeczności naukowej w obszarze HS.

Filar „Wspieranie biblioróżnorodności” pozostaje w centrum zainteresowania OPERAS, co potwierdzają takie inicjatywy jak DIAMAS, mapujący zróżnicowany ekosystem diamentowego modelu otwartego dostępu, czy PALOMERA, analizujący polityki otwartego dostępu do monografii w Europejskiej Przestrzeni Badawczej. Szczególnym sukcesem tego roku był dynamiczny rozwój modelu diamentowego: w krajach członkowskich obserwowaliśmy działania zmierzające do wzmocnienia krajowych ekosystemów, tworzenia krajowych konsorcjów oraz konsolidacji zaangażowania w zrównoważone, oddolne modele wydawnicze. Ruch ten ma nie tylko fundamentalne znaczenie dla społeczności naukowej, lecz także odzwierciedla szersze wartości, takie jak otwartość, współpraca i odporność w czasach niepewności.

Wreszcie, filar „Wzmacnianie jakości” realizowaliśmy poprzez tworzenie ram zarządzania ryzykiem i dbałość o wysoką jakość wyników naszych projektów. W 2024 roku OPERAS osiągnęła też znaczący postęp w rozwoju narzędzi, doprowadzając do etapu pełnej operacyjności trzy nowe usługi (VERA, Metrics i OPERAS-ID). Jest to kolejny krok w kierunku dostarczania stabilnych, precyzyjnie zdefiniowanych i w pełni funkcjonalnych rozwiązań, które podnoszą jakość i dostępność dorobku naukowego w dziedzinie nauk społecznych i humanistycznych.

Należy podkreślić, że prace w ramach każdego z tych filarów realizowaliśmy w ramach licznych projektów międzynarodowych. Świadczy to nie tylko o dynamice społeczności skupionej wokół OPERAS, gotowej do inicjowania, prowadzenia i uczestniczenia we wspólnych przedsięwzięciach, lecz także o świadomym i strategicznym rozwoju infrastruktury badawczej. Rozwój ten obejmuje zróżnicowane obszary działania, a jednocześnie pozostaje spójny z kluczową linią strategiczną OPERAS. Z myślą o przyszłości OPERAS już teraz zapewnił sobie stabilne fundamenty dalszego rozwoju, m.in. dzięki skutecznemu pozyskiwaniu nowych środków finansowych. Realizowane dziś projekty umożliwią wykorzystanie sztucznej inteligencji i grafów wiedzy w usługach OPERAS, a także zapewnienie interdyscyplinarnego wsparcia dla diamentowego modelu publikowania. O tych wszystkich osiągnięciach poinformujemy szerzej w przyszłorocznym raporcie.

Niniejszy raport pokazuje, że OPERAS ugruntowuje pozycję infrastruktury badawczej o kluczowym znaczeniu dla swoich głównych społeczności. Dla członków i węzłów krajowych stanowi narzędzie do realizacji ważnych celów programowych oraz wspólnego świadczenia usług dla grup docelowych w różnych krajach. Badaczom i badaczkom oferuje wsparcie, narzędzia i wiedzę, przyczyniając się do doskonalenia komunikacji naukowej w SSH. Decydentom politycznym czy instytucjom finansującym dostarcza danych i analiz wspierających podejmowanie świadomych decyzji. Różnorodnym organizacjom, inicjatywom i infrastrukturom tematycznym w naukach HS zapewnia zaś przekrojowe i interdyscyplinarne kompetencje, praktycznie wspierające koordynację ich działań w zakresie komunikacji naukowej. Wreszcie, OPERAS służy społeczeństwu jako trwała infrastruktura wspierająca debatę publiczną, demokrację i wolność, nie tylko ułatwiając przepływ wiedzy, lecz także urzeczywistniając nadrzędne wartości zaangażowania i współpracy na skalę globalną.

Mówiąc najprościej, OPERAS jest obecny tam, gdzie jest najbardziej potrzebny, aby sprostać najważniejszym wyzwaniom związanym z komunikacją naukową, otwartą nauką i społeczeństwem. Każdego roku zwiększa się jego wpływ na te kluczowe obszary dzięki silnej, międzynarodowej i rozwijającej się społeczności.

Dr Maciej Maryl

Członek Zgromadzenia Zarządzającego OPERAS, Koordynator OPERAS-PL, Kierownik Centrum Humanistyki Cyfrowej Instytutu Badań Literackich PAN.

OPERAS - Vision, Mission & Development

Definition and Mission

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area. Its mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH.

Vision

OPERAS' aim is to make Open Science a reality for research in the SSH and achieve a scholarly communication system where knowledge produced in the SSH benefits researchers, academics, students and more generally the whole society across Europe and worldwide, without barriers.

Development and Milestones of OPERAS

The European landscape of scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) is currently patchy, fragmented and not organised enough to be efficient, particularly to address the challenge of transitioning to Open Science. This is due to several factors, such as the small size of resource providers, the historical underfunding and lack of sustainability in this area, the variety of technical skills and resources across the community. The nature of the SSH disciplines also adds specific challenges which are not correctly addressed at scale, such as the diversity of publication languages, the entrenchment in diverse cultural backgrounds and the need for specific forms of scholarly communication (monographs, critical editions, and edited bibliographies, amongst others). OPERAS was created to deal with all these issues and to build a strong, aligned and empowering SSH community for all: researchers, librarians, small editors and the whole scholarly community within the European Research Area.

OPERAS

2016-2017

About the development and milestones of OPERAS:

The idea for OPERAS as a research infrastructure was conceived during a conference, where Pierre Mounier, Eelco Ferwerda, and Margo Bargheer initiated discussions around the need for a more integrated approach. During that period, similar discussions were happening among peers – that would later become core members of OPERAS. They soon began collaborating on project proposals, resulting in the launch of **OPERAS-D (the design project for the infrastructure)** and HIRMEOS in January 2017.

2018

By January 2018, **Working Groups** were established to advance both the conceptual and practical development of the infrastructure. These groups later evolved into Special Interest Groups, enabling deeper community engagement and thematic focus. In June 2018, **Pierre Mounier** shared the coordination responsibilities with **Suzanne Dumouchel**, becoming co-coordinators.

2019

Within the Preparation Project of OPERAS, **OPERAS-P**, the **OPERAS Coordination Team** was formally established in November 2019, and in the same month the founding papers for OPERAS AISBL were signed.

2020

Finally, in March 2020, **OPERAS AISBL** was established under the Belgian law on non-for-profit associations, international non-for-profit associations and foundations of 27 June 1921, as amended by the Law of 2 May 2002. As an AISBL, OPERAS pursues a non-profit purpose of international utility. Chloé Lebon was the first Secretary General, seconded by the [Centre national de la recherche scientifique \(CNRS\)](#).

2021

A major milestone was reached in June 2021 when OPERAS was included in the **ESFRI Roadmap 2021**, recognising its strategic importance in the European research landscape. In October 2021, **Yannick Legré** joined OPERAS as its Secretary General and the first official employee of OPERAS AISBL, establishing the OPERAS office in Brussels.

2022-2024

In 2022, the **OPERAS-PLUS** project was launched, marking a significant step toward making OPERAS fully operational as an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) by 2028 — paving the way for its long-term sustainability as an efficient and open scholarly communication infrastructure for the Social Sciences and Humanities. In **2024**, the OPERAS Coordination Team (OCT) comprised 21 people (18.9 FTE), including 14 AISBL employees (12.9 FTE) working from 10 different countries.

Activities & Progress

Making Open Science a reality for
research in the Social Sciences
and Humanities

Activities highlights

OPERAS events, publications and milestones

Webinar on the European Landscape of Institutional Publishing (DIAMAS report)

12 March, online

CRAFT-OA: 1st Summer School for Journal Editors

<https://www.craft-oa.eu/report-summer-school-2024/>
27 May - 1 June in Masaryk University Center in Telč, Czech Republic

VERA Hub (OPERAS service) available in 7 languages

Publication: The European landscape of institutional publishing - A synopsis of results from the DIAMAS survey

<https://zenodo.org/records/10551710>

31 January

OPERAS-SI: Slovenian National Node kick-off meeting

27 May

2024

February

April

June

January

March

May

July

First webinar of the cross-project collaboration between CRAFT-OA; DIAMAS and PALOMERA: Creating Community-Driven Pathways to Equitable Open Scholarly Publishing – Where Are We Now,

<https://operas.hypotheses.org/6990>

27 February, online

Release of the reports of the exploratory studies for creating a technology-aided collaborative translation service dedicated to open scholarly communication:

<https://operas.hypotheses.org/7231>

15 April

OPERAS Conference 2024: Opening collaboration for community-driven scholarly communication

<https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/operas-conference-2024/>

24-26 April in Zadar, Croatia

Advocating for Responsible Research Assessment: workshop by the OPERAS Advocacy SIG

<https://operas.hypotheses.org/7395>

26 April in Zadar, Croatia

Events

Publications

Milestones

In 2024, OPERAS undertook a range of activities to strengthen its network, the research infrastructure itself and actively engage with community members and stakeholder groups. This page highlights key moments from the year, showcasing the diversity and impact of OPERAS' activities.

TrustOn2024 - Tackling Disinformation: Let's build a human-centric and trustworthy digital future! Workshop Under the auspices of the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the European Union <https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/truston-2024/>
26 - 27 June at the Royal Library of Belgium (KBR) - Brussels

PALOMERA Final Conference
<https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/palomera-conference/>
28 - 29 October in Ljubljana, Slovenia

Publication of the PALOMERA Recommendations for Open Access Books
<https://zenodo.org/records/14049032>
07 November

4th Training Session of GraspOS: Leveraging OPERAS Metrics: showing the impact of Open Access books
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jyTIZGVICTw>
26 November, online

September

December

2025

August

October

November

Science Summit of the 79th United Nations General Assembly (UNGA79): Session "Fostering Trust in the Digital Sphere: A Multi-Stakeholder Approach Introduction" organised by OPERAS
11 September, online

The Digital Governance Series at the UN Science Summit 2024 - Transforming Science in the Age of AI and Digital Innovation, Session: Defining Digital Citizen Science. Presentation: Empowering citizen science in the social sciences and humanities: the VERA platform
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cdhG69g-lel&list=PLCq6DL5loCAIffEKSHgBnVbvX9HplnFn7&index=10>
17 September, online

The Digital Governance Series at the UN Science Summit 2024 - Transforming Science in the Age of AI and Digital Innovation: Session: Science Systems Humanity in the age of AI. Discussion: Responding Perspectives on Equity and Inclusion on Alan Kay's keynote.
18 September, online

OPERAS listed in the POSSE community
Applying the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure \(POSI\)](https://operas.hypotheses.org/7796)
<https://operas.hypotheses.org/7796>
25 September

Soft Launch of the National Node: OPERAS-UK
05 December, online

OPERAS 2024 Retrospective
Video series
https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLNSNT11cPt5bj2iP_z3ZP5IXBuxfkkpju

Key Efforts in Focus ▶

OPERAS Conference 2024 **Opening collaboration for community-** **driven scholarly communication** **24–26 April 2024, Zadar, Croatia**

The European Council called in May 2023 for transparent, equitable, and open access to scholarly publications. For European public research and innovation actors, scholarly knowledge is a public good. Publicly funded research and its results should be immediately and openly available without barriers such as subscription fees or paywalls. This is essential in driving knowledge forward, promoting innovation and tackling social issues.

OPERAS welcomes this Council Conclusion that fits with our aim to make Open Science a reality for Social Sciences and Humanities, and we are convinced we can only achieve this with collaboration, opening collaboration for community-driven scholarly communication. This is why we chose this theme for our **2024 OPERAS conference**.

This conference was organised by the OPERAS-PLUS project to support the development of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, supporting open scholarly communication for Social Sciences and Humanities in the European Research Area and to open up collaboration and facilitate exchange.

The OPERAS Conference 2024 was a **discussion hub** in which different stakeholders such as researchers, decision-makers, publishers, librarians, and institutional service providers could share and compare their take on the current scholarly communication system and their vision for a sustainable future. The conference addressed issues relevant to the Social Sciences and Humanities field in the Open Science paradigm involving equitable publishing, multilingualism, bibliodiversity, and other related topics.

12 workshops

40 presentations

27 posters

1 panel discussion

10 sessions

3 keynotes

Key Efforts in Focus ▶

TrustOn2024 - Tackling Disinformation

Let's build a human-centric and trustworthy digital future!

Aligned with the United Nations' vision of a more trusted digital future, this international workshop, organised by OPERAS in June 2024, highlighted a human-centric approach and moved beyond technology-only solutions. It positioned itself at the forefront of developing actionable strategies, providing **practical recommendations for the UN Summit of the Future in September 2024**. This workshop took place under the auspices of the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the European Union at the Royal Library of Belgium (KBR) in Brussels on 26–27 June 2024 with the support of Belspo (Belgian Science Policy). In order to shed light on the topic from different perspectives, the workshop was organised around 3 different discussion tracks: **Infrastructure Trust, Mediation Trust and Science Trust**.

The workshop aimed:

- ▶ To assess various trust dimensions of the Internet, encompassing infrastructure, governance & regulation, mediation and science, through partnerships with civil society, academia, the tech community, youth, policymakers, and others.
- ▶ To establish a multi-stakeholder collaboration model, inspired by community living labs, as a fundamental step in developing responsible Digital Public Infrastructures (DPIs), a key element of the United Nations Global Digital Compact.
- ▶ To share academic editorial best practices to safeguard the quality and integrity of online content, which is paramount in the age of AI-driven disinformation.

The workshop laid the groundwork for a series of further OPERAS participations in events on this topic. At the forefront of developing actionable strategies, OPERAS is committed to providing practical recommendations that incorporate diverse perspectives and expertise. In 2024, the preparation of the publication of the TrustOn2024 workshop report marked another significant milestone in OPERAS' ongoing commitment to promoting trust in science and digital communication. The report was published in January 2025 under the title **"Fostering Trust in the Digital Age" on Zenodo**: <https://zenodo.org/records/14621383>, uniting global voices in infrastructure, science and mediation, and laying the groundwork for actionable, collaborative solutions to counter disinformation worldwide.

3 discussion tracks

3 round tables

38 talks

3 plenaries

74 participants

Key Efforts in Focus ▶

Bringing OPERAS Services to Users

In 2024, the committed OPERAS Services Task Force orchestrated a series of events dedicated to showcasing and advancing the OPERAS services. These events brought the spotlight to the OPERAS service catalogue that is driving forward open scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities across the European Research Area.

OPERAS Services Catalogue presentations:

- ▶ OPERAS Conference 2024 (April, Zadar) - Full catalogue
- ▶ E-RIHS Public Event (24 Sept, Florence) - Full catalogue
- ▶ CONFOA 2024 (01 Oct, Porto) - Full catalogue

Events with a focus on each particular service:

GoTriple

- ▶ ATRIUM Researcher Forum on GoTriple (17 Oct, Poznan)
- ▶ OPERAS-FR: National Node event on GoTriple (5 July, online)
- ▶ TrustOn 2024 (26 Jun, Brussels) - GoTriple

vera activating research

- ▶ VERA at UN Science Summit (17 Sep, online)
- ▶ TrustOn 2024 (27 Jun, Brussels)
- ▶ Liber Conference 2024 (4 Jul, Limassol)
- ▶ Comunidades de Ciência Aberta na UC (6 May, Coimbra)
- ▶ Trieste Next festival (28 September, Trieste)
- ▶ VERA Workshop at the University of Macerata (1 October, Macerata)
- ▶ CeOS_SE Workshop at the University of Turin (4 October, Turin)
- ▶ Final conference of project "Citizen-Enhanced Open Science in Southeastern Europe Higher Education Knowledge Hubs (CeOS_SE)". (October 30, 2024, Zagreb)

PRISM

- ▶ GraspOS Webinar on PRISM (14 May, online)

Metrics

- ▶ GraspOS Webinar on Metrics (26 Nov, online)

Key Efforts in Focus ▶

OPERAS 2024 Retrospective

In December 2024, OPERAS curated, produced, and published a retrospective video series on the OPERAS YouTube channel, showcasing key achievements, milestones, developments, and news from the open scholarly communication community across the European Research Area for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). This initiative aimed to celebrate the progress made throughout 2024 and to highlight the contributions of OPERAS within the broader SSH ecosystem.

We invite you to explore the highlights of our journey and the impact we have collectively made. The complete playlist, comprising 14 videos, is available on our YouTube channel: <https://bit.ly/retrospective-2024-youtube>

The following topics were featured in the retrospective series:

The 5 year anniversary of the OPERAS AISBL creation

The OPERAS Conference 2024

Highlights of the OPERAS blog in 2024

Growth of the OPERAS community and welcome to new members in 2024

OPERAS website insights

OPERAS Metrics service

OPERAS Innovation Lab

GoTriple platform and its improvements in 2024

OPERAS National Nodes

OPERAS Future Services and the example of MONDAECUS

TrustOn2024

Projects in 2024 and its activities

OPERAS Special Interest Groups

OPERAS Newsletter

OPERAS Strategic Plan & Objectives 2023–25

A robust strategic plan to develop and strengthen the profile of the research infrastructure

The OPERAS Strategic Plan serves as a leading framework for all OPERAS activities, shaping its priorities and directions. It also informs decisions on project & collaboration involvement, ensuring alignment with the development and strengthening of the research infrastructure.

The current OPERAS Strategic Plan is the result of multiple approaches. As part of the OPERAS-P project, a Strategic Plan (2019–2022) outlining the vision, mission, core values and pillars of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure has been defined to support the application for the ESFRI roadmap. A lot of concrete results have already been achieved during these first 3 years, e.g. the structuration of the Association, the initial development of OPERAS services, the establishment of partnerships and the set-up of several national nodes as it was highlighted in the Annual Reports 2020 to 2023.

The vision, mission, core values and pillars of the Strategic Plan remain the same within the current strategy, the focus of this update is on the objectives and action points, representing further implementation of the infrastructure. This strategic plan was

a collaborative approach between the OPERAS coordination team and the Executive Assembly in 2022 and 2023 during the current project *OPERAS-PLUS - On the road to sustainability: paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure*. The project receives funding from the Horizon Europe framework Infra-Dev under Grant Agreement Number 101079608 (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079608>) in order to support new ESFRI research infrastructure projects in their preparatory phase.

2023–2025 Objectives matrix

Area / Topic → ↓	Redesigning ecosystem	Empowering community	Supporting bibliodiversity	Fostering quality
Governance and coordination	(O1) OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the SSH Open ScholComm communities		(O2) The Diamond Open Access model supported as a major one in the scholarly communication ecosystem	
Portfolio of services		(O3) OPERAS services published and integrated with EOSC and other marketplaces and communities (regional, national, international)		(O4) Clear set of well-defined and operational services
Training and outreach		(O5) OPERAS members and communities are trained and knowledgeable in SSH FAIR and Open Science practices		(O6) OPERAS members are trained and knowledgeable in SSH open science service delivery

Policy advising	(O7) OPERAS as a trusted advisor for national and European Open Science strategies		(O8) Academic books are included in the Open Science policies	
Innovation		(O9) Supporting innovative scholarly outputs and services		

The following provides a detailed overview of the OPERAS objectives, also in relation to the projects and OPERAS bodies:

OBJECTIVE 1. | OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the Social Sciences and Humanities and Open Scholarly Communication communities.

It prepares the transition to become an ERIC as well as all the human resources aspects now that OPERAS AISBL has its employees. Several tasks are necessary to strengthen the governance and administrative aspects of the Research Infrastructure, in particular in the setting up of its national node in at least 10 countries in Europe. The efficiency of the organisation must be seen at the crossroads of a well-structured organisation with defined processes and a flexible and agile management of the activities, taking into account the SSH communities it serves.

SUPPORTED AND DRIVEN IN 2024 BY: *the OPERAS Coordination Team, the Executive Assembly, the General Assembly, the Board of Governing Representatives, the Special Interest Group - Advocacy and the OPERAS members as a whole, as partly in-kind contribution, and by all projects, especially OPERAS-PLUS*

OBJECTIVE 2. | The Diamond Open Access model is supported as a major one in the scholarly communication ecosystem.

As a result of the analysis of different Open Access (OA) models, the Diamond OA financing model, which does not require authors to pay fees for their research to be published, nor readers to pay for reading publications is in its early stages of development, but is seen as the most fair and equitable open access model. As a research infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication, OPERAS is naturally closely linked to this model.

SUPPORTED AND DRIVEN IN 2024 BY: *the programme European Diamond Capacity Hub, which is fiscally hosted by OPERAS, Special Interest Group - Open Access Business Models and the Special Interest Group - Best Practices, and the projects CRAFT-OA & DIAMAS*

OBJECTIVE 3. | OPERAS services are published and integrated with EOSC and other marketplaces and communities (regional, national, international).

Visibility of OPERAS services is a key component to ensuring that target audiences are reached and the uptake of services is increased. This strategic objective takes a multi-pronged strategy by not limiting service discoverability to single sources that are owned and operated by OPERAS (i.e. website) and aims to leverage a variety of channels at regional, national, European and international levels (i.e. EOSC Marketplace). OPERAS is also planning to reuse European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) core services such as the helpdesk or others for its own services. This will be done in coordination with the other SSH Research Infrastructures (SSHOC Tier 1).

SUPPORTED AND DRIVEN IN 2024 BY: *the OPERAS Coordination Team, the Scientific Advisory Committee, the Services and Technology Board, Special Interest Group - Tools and Platforms, and by the projects OPERAS-PLUS, ATRIUM, Skills4EOSC, CRAFT-OA & GraspOS*

OBJECTIVE 4. | Clear set of well-defined and operational services.

This objective covers the full service delivery lifecycle comprising the planning, development, operation, maintenance and improvement of the OPERAS service portfolio. This includes service strategies and roadmaps that will be created and periodically updated to ensure relevance, overall strategic alignment and promotion. In order to harmonise implementation approaches across a multi-provider federation, a formal management system will be developed to underpin continued professionalisation based on well-known standards such as ISO 9000 (Quality Management) and FitSM (IT Service Management) with the aim of achieving organisational certification in the coming years.

SUPPORTED AND DRIVEN 2024: *by the OPERAS Coordination Team, the Scientific Advisory Committee, the Services and Technology Board, and by the project OPERAS-PLUS & ATRIUM*

OBJECTIVE 5. | OPERAS members and communities are trained and knowledgeable in SSH FAIR and Open Science practices

The objective is to ensure consistent knowledge of FAIR and Open Science, and support the development of participatory research and Citizen Science as well. The targets are the OPERAS members gathered in the Special Interest Groups, the SSH communities, and the civil society. The objective will be achieved through the definition of essential Open Science skills, the design of training modules, and the set-up of learning paths for all the actors of research in the SSH field.

SUPPORTED AND DRIVEN IN 2024 BY: *OPERAS Coordination Team, the OPERAS members, the Special Interest Group - Common Standards and FAIR principles, and the projects OPERAS-PLUS, Skills4EOSC, ATRIUM & GraspOS*

OBJECTIVE 6. | OPERAS members are trained and knowledgeable in SSH open science service delivery

Training and knowledge sharing is a core principle that facilitates a collaborative environment and provides confidence to both users and providers. This objective uses a mix of both formal training and certification, informational webinars and presentations, as well as practical hands-on workshops that are tailored to the content and target audience. Activity coverage includes specific areas such as on the individual OPERAS services, the FitSM standard (Service Management), as well as other more general topics such as OPERAS service alignment with EOSC and FAIR requirements, OPERAS Integrated Management System for Federation Members, and services and service delivery models in SSH open science.

SUPPORTED AND DRIVEN IN 2024 BY: *OPERAS Coordination Team, and the projects OPERAS-PLUS & Skills4EOSC*

OBJECTIVE 7. | OPERAS as a trusted advisor for national and European Open Science strategies

OPERAS aims at representing the SSH community in the creation, development, update and implementation of the national and European Open Science strategies, especially by focusing on open scholarly communication practices and in particular Open Access publications. OPERAS will contribute to these policies by developing relevant services to serve the needs but also by coordinating its diversity of stakeholders, amongst them the SSH researchers, in their expectations to develop successful Open Science practices. Through strategic collaborations and partnerships, OPERAS continues to strengthen its position as a trusted advisor.

SUPPORTED AND DRIVEN IN 2024 BY: *OPERAS coordination team, and the projects CRAFT-OA, DIAMAS, OPERAS-PLUS, Skills4EOSC & Translations and Open Science*

OBJECTIVE 8. | Academic books are included in the Open Science policies

Open Science policies and strategies are potential game changers that can drive more open access to scholarly communication. However, Open Access book policies are still few and far between in the European Research Area. This objective has as its focus to help research funding organisations, research performing organisations, and Open Access policy-makers at the national level to make well-informed OA book policies and strategies that align on a shared vision of OA to books, respecting diversity, equity, and inclusion. Facilitating an increase in OA book policies and strategies will help accelerate the transition to OA for books.

SUPPORTED AND DRIVEN IN 2024 BY: *OPERAS Coordination Team, Special Interest Group - Open Access Books Network, and the projects OAEBUDT GBB & PALOMERA*

OBJECTIVE 9. | Supporting innovative scholarly outputs and services

This objective focuses on providing tailored guidance on the implementation of innovative scholarly outputs in SSH to different OPERAS stakeholders, in particular authors (of texts, data, code), and developing services to support them. Increasing numbers of researchers in SSH are using innovative outputs to present their work. However, they often lack proper expertise or encounter obstacles in their institutions or evaluation frameworks which do not recognise nontraditional work. Thus, a multi-stakeholder, systemic approach is needed to provide support and recognition for innovative scholarly communication. This objective, stemming from the Future of Scholarly Communication report¹, will be addressed by establishing the OPERAS Innovation Lab as the knowledge hub for the OPERAS community, providing guidelines and counselling to stakeholders wishing to engage with innovative outputs, as well liaising between those stakeholders and relevant e-infrastructure providers. This work will be carried out in the OPERAS-PLUS project.

SUPPORTED AND DRIVEN IN 2024 BY: *Special Interest Group - Best practices, and the projects OPERAS-PLUS & Translations and Open Science*

¹ Avanço, K., Balula, A., Błaszczńska, M., Buchner, A., Caliman, L., Clivaz, C., Costa, C., Franczak, M., Gatti, R., Giglia, E., Gingold, A., Jarmelo, S., Padez, M. J., Leão, D., Maryl, M., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Mojsak, K., Morka, A., Mosterd, T., ... Wieneke, L. (2021). Future of Scholarly Communication . Forging an inclusive and innovative research infrastructure for scholarly communication in Social Sciences and Humanities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5017705>

▶ 1. OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient Organisation highly representing the Social Sciences and Humanities OpenScholComm communities

OPERAS advancing its multi-stakeholder framework on its way to becoming an ERIC

In 2024, OPERAS continued its road to sustainability; paving the way for OPERAS as an efficient open Social Sciences and Humanities scholarly communication Research Infrastructure to become an ERIC in Q4 2027 or Q1 2028. In order to prepare for this important step, OPERAS AISBL has worked on a new governance structure by expanding its types of memberships. Indeed, five challenges have been foreseen:

- ▶ High risk for OPERAS to depend too much on projects funding
- ▶ Structural funding of OPERAS: unbalanced contribution from France through in-kind and regular ad-hoc subventions
- ▶ How to prepare ourselves to transition towards the funding structure of the ERIC
- ▶ GA members must have a more formal commitment to the AISBL (not possible in the Statutes actually)
- ▶ OPERAS must prepare for the potential valley of death between the end of the current infra dev and the launch of the ERIC

The year 2024 marked a significant step forward for OPERAS with the establishment of the **Board of Governing Representatives** (BGR). The first meeting was held on January 9th, followed by two other sessions in June and November 2024. These meetings laid the groundwork for critical developments throughout the year and several important discussions on OPERAS as a sustainable research infrastructure.

Key achievements for OPERAS included the submission of the First Step Application and the preparation of a **first draft of the OPERAS ERIC Statutes**. In parallel, OPERAS advanced the Technical and Scientific Description (TSD) of the Research Infrastructure and initiated discussions regarding the structure and level of membership fees for the ERIC.

2024 proved to be a particularly challenging year, marked by political transitions and elections across several European countries, leading to periods of uncertainty and instability. Nevertheless, the General Assembly reaffirmed its confidence in OPERAS and its long-term vision.

Members

Connecting European Stakeholders in the Social Sciences and Humanities & Collaborating towards an open scholarly communication ecosystem

OPERAS members form a dynamic and collaborative network of institutions dedicated to advancing open scholarly communication across the European research area and beyond. Bringing together (university) publishers, libraries, research institutions, and infrastructure providers, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises and other research infrastructures, they foster innovation, share expertise, and contribute engagedly to the development of OPERAS as a research infrastructure. By actively shaping OPERAS' services, recommendations, and strategic direction within the Special Interest Groups and beyond, members play a key role in strengthening the whole research infrastructure. OPERAS exists only because of its dynamic and diverse members and flourishes continuously thanks to them.

OPERAS has 69 members in 25 countries, welcoming 7 of them in 2024

Australia
Austria
Belgium
Brazil
Canada
Croatia
Cyprus
Denmark
Finland
France
Georgia
Germany
Greece
Italy
Luxembourg
Netherlands
Norway
Poland
Portugal
Serbia
Slovenia
Spain
Switzerland
Sweden
United Kingdom

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Core Members

Core members of OPERAS AISBL actively participate in both the Assembly of the Commons and the Executive Assembly, contributing the equivalent of 20% of a full-time position (in-kind), and hold voting rights in both bodies. They also support the association financially through an annual membership fee of € 5,000.

Max Weber
Stiftung

University of Zadar
Universitas Studiorum
Jadertina | 1396 | 2002 |

UNIVERSITÀ
DI TORINO

NATIONAL DOCUMENTATION CENTRE

Federation of Finnish
Learned Societies

UNIVERSIDADE D
COIMBRA

ZRC SAZU

Supporting Members

Supporting members of OPERAS AISBL participate in the General Assembly and contribute to the organisation through an annual membership fee of € 10,000.

Délégation générale
à la langue française
et aux langues de France

NIEDERSÄCHSISCHE STAATS- UND
UNIVERSITÄTSBIBLIOTHEK GÖTTINGEN

Ordinary Members

Ordinary members of OPERAS AISBL take part in at least one Special Interest Group, contributing the equivalent of 10% of a full-time post (in-kind), and hold voting rights in the Assembly of Commons.

UNIVERSITÄT
BERN

]a[akademie der bildenden künste wien

Instituto Universitário de Lisboa

Ordinary Members

New Ordinary Members in 2024*

*in order of entry

Thoth (UK)

Thoth is a metadata management and dissemination platform and service specifically tailored to tackle the problems of getting Open Access books into the wider supply chain. Thoth enables publishers to ingest, create, manage and export fully open, CC0-licensed metadata for their books in a variety of formats and platform-specific flavours of e.g. MARC, KBART, JSON, and ONIX via open APIs, and facilitates the dissemination of OA books to metadata and content aggregator platforms as well as into repositories participating in the Thoth Archiving Network.

For more information visit: <https://thoth.pub/>

Open Book Collective (UK)

The Open Book Collective is a UK-registered charity that brings together publishers, publishing service providers, and scholarly libraries to secure the diversity and financial futures of open access book production and dissemination.

For more information visit: <https://openbookcollective.org/>

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Royal Danish Library (Denmark)

The Royal Danish Library is the national library of Denmark and the university library of the University of Copenhagen and Roskilde University.

In 2017 it merged with the State and University Library in Aarhus to form a combined national library.

It is among the largest libraries in the world and the largest in the Nordic countries.

The Royal Danish Library hosts several Open Access collections in their portfolio that all can be found at the website: <https://www.kb.dk/en>

Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (Poland)

Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center

Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC) affiliated to the Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry of the Polish Academy of Sciences is an internationally known

node of the European Research Area in the field of IT infrastructure of science and an important R&D center in the field of information and communication technologies (ICT). As a development centre of e-Infrastructure, PSNC designed and built the Metropolitan Network POZMAN, High Performance Computing Center and the national broadband network PIONIER, maintained and still developed by PSNC.

Projects developed at PSNC include cooperation with almost a thousand units from over 60 countries in the world, on six continents. All projects are focused on IT technology and concern new generation networks, grids, portals, digital libraries, IT energy efficiency, climate, weather, air quality, new sources of energy, digital humanities, personalized medicine, intelligent agriculture, industry 4.0, astronomy, bioinformatics, Big Data analysis, artificial intelligence, New Media, education, Smart City, cyber security. The list of areas of activity in which PSNC undertakes work is constantly expanding, providing an important example of taking up new technological challenges.

About: <https://www.psnk.pl>

EASSH (France)

EASSH is the largest advocacy and science policy organisation for the social sciences and humanities in Europe.

The alliance has over 70 member organisations including a wide range of disciplinary areas, stakeholders and universities from across Europe – and encompassing over 100,000 researchers.

About: <https://eassh.eu/>

University of Bielefeld (Germany)

Bielefeld University Library is a pioneer of the Open Access movement in Germany. In 2005, Bielefeld University adopted the first Open Access policy at a German university. Since 2004, the University Library has been developing

and operating the academic search engine BASE, which now indexes over 400 million references from over 11,000 data providers (including repositories, journals and digital collections), displays the Open Access status of each document as far as possible and makes it accessible. Other contributions of Bielefeld University Library to the Open Access infrastructure are OpenAPC, an open data service for transparent monitoring of fee-based Open Access publishing, and oa.finder, a service to make it easier for researchers to find a suitable publication medium for their Open Access publication, taking various criteria into account.

Bielefeld University Library has contributed its expertise to numerous international (e.g. DRIVER, Europeana,

OpenAIRE, PALOMERA) and national projects. As part of the “German Service Centre for Diamond Open Access”, funded by the German Research Foundation from 2025 until 2028, Bielefeld University Library will create a database-supported registry for Diamond Open Access journal titles in Germany.

For more information please visit: uni-bielefeld.de/ub/

University of Silesia in Katowice (Poland)

UNIVERSITY OF SILESIA
IN KATOWICE

The University of Silesia in Katowice is the largest in Silesia and one of the largest in Poland – it educates more than 18,000 students in 8 faculties. The university is engaged in open science – it has introduced an Institutional Openness Policy and an innovative research data management program called “Data Steward.” Also associated with open science at the University are the Center for Scientific Information and Academic Library (CINiBA) and the University of Silesia Press, which publishes 44 academic journals and numerous monographs through dedicated open access platforms (journals.us.edu.pl and monograph.us.edu.pl). As part of its efforts to improve science assessment systems, the University has joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). The University is represented by 468 researchers in the humanities and 386 in the social sciences, among them a group of researchers associated with digital humanities and numerous interdisciplinary studies. The university pursues various grants and extensive international collaborations.

About: <https://us.edu.pl/en/>

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

OPERAS and its bodies

Governing a distributed research infrastructure collectively

Coordination Team

The core of OPERAS' daily activities

The OPERAS Coordination Team supports, liaises with and advises the Executive Assembly and all the different bodies of OPERAS. It provides various coordination, management and secretariat functions for the OPERAS Research Infrastructure to support the operation and the building of OPERAS as an ERIC in the following areas: Strategy and Policy; Legal and Finance; Community and Communication; Service Management and Technical Coordination; National Nodes; and Project Management and Planning.

In December 2024, the OPERAS Coordination Team met for four days at the OPERAS headquarters in Brussels, Belgium, to receive training in multi- and intercultural communication, to discuss the OPERAS Strategic Plan 2026-2028 and to evaluate the training, service and funding strategy.

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Coordinator (Community)

Pierre Mounier
EHESS

Coordinator (Partnerships)

Suzanne Dumouchel
CNRS

Secretary General

Yannick Legré

Chief Technology Officer

Sy Holsinger

Technical Manager
(CRAFT-OA project)

Maxim Kupreyev

Service Marketing &
Community Outreach
Officer
(ATRIUM, GraspOS,
Skills4EOSC)

Carol Delmazo

Service Marketing &
Community Outreach Officer
(OPERAS-PLUS, CRAFT-OA,
Skills4EOSC)

(joined in 2024)

Elena Sokolova

Chief Finance &
Administration Officer

Céline Bitoune

Project Manager
(PALOMERA)

Mandy Lin

Administrative/
Finance
Assistant

(joined in 2024)

**Jamila
Sahraoui**

Capacity Building Manager

Karla Avanço
OpenEdition

Liaison to OPERAS
National nodes

Drahomira Cupar
University of Zadar

Community Manager
(EDCH)

*(selected in 2024,
joined in January 2025)*

Marion Paulhae

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Citizen Science Officer

Alessia Smaniotto
OpenEdition

FAIR Data Officer

Arnaud Gingold
OpenEdition

Scientific Coordinator
(Translations and Open Science Project)

Susanna Fiorini

Project Community Manager
(OA Book Usage Data Trust, GRAPHIA and PALOMERA)

Ursula Rabar

Open Science Project Officer
(Skills4EOSC and DIAMAS)

Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou

Open Science Project Officer
(DIAMAS)

Sona Lisa Arasteh-Roodsary

Project Policy Officer
(Skills4EOSC, GraspOS)

Fotis Mystakopoulos

Communication Manager

Marlen Töpfer
Max Weber Stiftung

Content and Communication Specialist

Lorena Caliman
University of Coimbra

Executive Assembly

Guiding the strategic direction and core activities of OPERAS through critical decision-making

The Executive Assembly is composed of 13 renowned organisations (= all OPERAS core members) from 13 European countries, committed to steer OPERAS towards full maturity. It is the day-to-day governing and decision-making body of the OPERAS AISBL, which meets monthly.

Franjo Pehar

University of Zadar, Croatia

Franjo Pehar is Associate Professor and Head of the Laboratory for Interactive Systems and User Experience. He also serves as the Director of the Doctoral Study “Knowledge Society and Transfer of Information” and is focused on scholarly communication, bibliometrics, digital publishing, and HCI.

Michael Kaiser

Max Weber Stiftung, Germany

Michael Kaiser is a historian and Director of the department perspectiva.net, library and IT affairs at the headquarters of the Max Weber Stiftung (MWS).

Lea Rynänen-Karjalainen

Federation of Finnish Learned Societies, Finland

Lea Rynänen-Karjalainen is the Executive Director of the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies since 2014. Before the Federation she has worked as the Vice Rector of the Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, senior science adviser at the Research Council of Finland and several university management positions.

Lionel Maurel

CNRS, France

Lionel Maurel is Scientific Deputy Director at the National Institute for Humanities and Social Sciences of the CNRS (French National Centre for Scientific Research). Two units in the CNRS are particularly involved in the development of the OPERAS AISBL: OpenEdition and Huma-Num.

Vassiliki Apostolopoulou

National Documentation Centre, Greece

She joined EKT as a Research Associate working on an EU-funded project focusing on scholarly communication and Open Science policies. She holds a PhD in Political Philosophy, and she is a postdoctoral researcher in the field of Performing Arts.

Elena Giglia

University of Turin, Italy

Elena Giglia, PhD in Italian literature, Masters’ Degree in Librarianship and Masters’ Degree in Public Institutions Management, is Head of the Open Access Office at the University of Turin.

Niels Stern

OAPEN, Netherlands

Niels Stern is Managing Director of OAPEN and Co-director of DOAB. He began his career in scholarly book publishing in 2003.

Monica Roos

erih+, Norway

Monica Roos is a Senior Advisor at The Norwegian Directorate for Higher Education and Skills. She has the overall responsibility for the technical and professional development erih+ and the Norwegian Registry. She has 20 years experience in Academic Publishing and Open Science.

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Maciej Maryl

The Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland

Maciej Maryl is Assistant Professor and Deputy Director of The Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IBL PAN) and founding head of the Digital Humanities Centre.

Delfim Leão

University of Coimbra, Portugal

Delfim Leão is Full Professor at the Institute of Classical Studies at the University of Coimbra. Former Director of Coimbra University Press (2011–2021), he is Vice-Rector for Culture, Communication and Open Science.

Aleš Pogačnik

The Research Center of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Slovenia

Aleš Pogacnik is Editor-in-chief and General Manager of Založba ZRC, publishing unit of ZRC SAZU. He holds an MA in Philosophy.

Pilar Rico-Castro

FECYT, Spain

Pilar Rico-Castro is Head of the Open Science Unit at FECYT National Representative at the National Points of Reference for Open Science and at the EOSC SB Expert Groups of the EC. National Expert at the Horizon Europe Programme Committee Research Infrastructures.

Graham Stone

Jisc, United Kingdom

Graham Stone is Jisc's subject matter expert for OA monographs. He is the Lead for Communications on OA monographs within Jisc and is responsible for developing and managing strategic relationships.

Frank Manista

Jisc / deputy, United Kingdom

Frank Manista is a Policy and Engagement Manager at Jisc. He engages with teams at Jisc who participate in EU-wide projects and ensures the awareness inside Jisc on the different engagements and the promotion outside, particularly around Open Access.

General Assembly

The highest decision-making body shaping the future of OPERAS and representing the entire research infrastructure

The General Assembly (GA) is the highest decision-making body and has the powers expressly granted to it by law or by the Articles of Association, in particular the following:

- ▶ Amendments to the Articles of Association
- ▶ Appointment and dismissal of the Statutory Auditor and the fixing of their remuneration
- ▶ Approval of the budget for the following financial year and of the annual accounts, as well as granting discharge to the Executive Assembly, the Secretary-General and the Statutory Auditor
- ▶ Voluntary dissolution of the Association
- ▶ Exclusion of Members.

The General Assembly (GA) is currently composed of EU and international infrastructures that commit to supporting the development of OPERAS, ministries (or proxies) from the countries where the core members are located, and the Chairs of the Assembly of the Commons (AoC), elected by their peers to represent the Ordinary Members at the GA. Members of the OCT attend in a supporting role. The General Assembly meets twice a year.

Represented in the General Assembly:

- ▶ Croatia
- ▶ Finland
- ▶ France
- ▶ Germany
- ▶ Greece
- ▶ Italy
- ▶ Netherlands
- ▶ Norway
- ▶ Poland
- ▶ Portugal
- ▶ Slovenia
- ▶ Spain
- ▶ United Kingdom

Supporting Members:

- ▶ DARIAH ERIC
- ▶ DGLFLF
- ▶ Göttingen SUB
- ▶ University of Nanterre

Ordinary Members:

- ▶ 2 Representatives of the Assembly of the Commons

Assembly of the Commons

Actively informing and involving the OPERAS community into the evolution of the Research Infrastructure

The Assembly of the Commons (AoC) gathered twice in 2024. The first AoC was held in April during the OPERAS Conference in Zadar and the second one in October 2024 online.

The purpose of the first Assembly of the Commons was to present the work of the Special Interest Groups and to discuss the role of the AoC going forward, including a presentation of OPERAS future governance.

During the second AoC meeting the second election of co-chairs took place. Vanessa Proudman and Mark Huskisson were 2024 re-elected for two years to serve as representatives of the Assembly of the Commons and to continue their roles in the General Assembly.

After the election, there was a presentation of the [OPERAS Innovation Lab](#) and of the service [Pathfinder](#).

Around 50% of the Ordinary Members were represented in the first meeting and 60% in the second one.

Vanessa Proudman is the Director of SPARC Europe with 20 years of management experience in facilitating access to knowledge through Open Access, Open Science, Open Culture and Open Education in Europe. She is advocating for change to increase more equitable access to knowledge through international, national and regional policy-making and extensive advocacy work. Prior to SPARC Europe, she worked at Tilburg University on various international initiatives, was programme manager at Europeana and led a department on information and IT at a UN-European region research institute in Vienna for over 10 years.

Mark Huskisson is responsible for Business Development at the Public Knowledge Project (PKP), the developer and stewards of OJS, OMP, and OPS. PKP develops open-source software systems that manage the complete scholarly publishing workflow for journals, monographs, and preprints, and conducting scholarly communication research on questions of Open Access and Open Science.

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Scientific Advisory Committee

13 experts of scientific excellence to guide OPERAS on ethical, technical and scientific matters

The OPERAS Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) is an independent body composed of currently thirteen experts of high scientific excellence from twelve countries, who advise, monitor and provide recommendations on the ethical, scientific and technical aspects of the infrastructure and its activities. It was established in December 2020.

The SAC is steered by its two co-chairs. A monthly online meeting is fostering ongoing discussions among the members on different topics.

In 2024, the OPERAS Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC) welcomed six new members, further strengthening its expertise and diversity. The following experts joined the committee: Alíz Horváth (Central European University, Vienna), Angeliki Tzouganatou (OpenAIRE AMKE), Paola Galimberti (University of Milan), and Christof Schöch (University of Trier). More recently, Carmen Brando (EHESS) and Mohamed Khemakhem (MandaNetwork, France) also joined the SAC, both bringing valuable expertise in Natural Language Processing (NLP) to support OPERAS' work on multilingualism and open scholarly infrastructures.

A key moment in the year was the SAC's in-person meeting during the OPERAS Conference in Zadar, Croatia. This face-to-face exchange enabled members to strengthen collaboration and engage in strategic discussions on the future of scholarly communication in the SSH field.

In addition to its advisory role, the SAC contributed to OPERAS' strategic reflections. Notably, SAC co-chair Jean-Claude Guédon authored a position paper entitled *Diamond Open Access in Scholarly Publishing: An Infrastructural and Historical Approach to its Governance*. The paper offers a historical overview and explores the governance of scholarly publishing infrastructures in the context of Diamond Open Access. It is available on the OPERAS website in the Living Book: <https://operas-eu.org/special-interest-group-living-book/diamond-open-access-in-scholarly-publishing-2024/>.

The SAC continues to play a vital role in supporting the OPERAS Executive Assembly by offering scientific insight and critical evaluation of initiatives aligned with the evolving needs of the SSH research community.

Elea Giménez Toledo

Jean-Claude Guédon

In 2022, the two new co-chairs of the OPERAS Scientific Advisory Committee were voted in:

Elea Giménez Toledo is a tenured Scientist at Institute of Philosophy, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) since 2006. She has a PhD in Library and Information Science (University Carlos III de Madrid) and is head of ILIA: Research Team on Scholarly Book, principal Investigator of Scholarly Publishers Indicators (SPI) and coordinator of ES CIENCIA Interdisciplinary Thematic Platform, an institutional project by CSIC on Spanish as a language of scientific communication. She has coordinated the reports on Spanish Academic Book Publishing developed for Federation of Spanish Publishers (FGEE) and the Association of Spanish University Presses (UNE).

Her research is focused on academic book publishing and its connection with research evaluation of humanist and social scientists. The relevance of the academic book industry in each country, the intrinsic value of the publication of results in monographs, quality in publishing, the manuscript selection processes, bibliodiversity, multilingualism in scholarly communication, digital transformation and open access transition for small and medium size publishers are fundamental axes of her research. She is now conducting a research project on scholarly book publishing at Iberoamerican level in collaboration with the Regional Center for the Promotion of Books in Latin America and Caribbean ([CERLALC](#)) and Association of Latin American and Caribbean university presses ([EULAC](#)). She is also leading, together with Gunnar Sivertsen (NIFU, Norway), the development of [Academic Book Publishers \(ABP\)](#): a global and multilingual register, an initiative backed by [ENRESSH](#) COST action.

▶ **Jean-Claude Guédon**, a historian of science by training, retired as “professeur honoraire” from the Université de Montréal at the end of 2018. His interest in scholarly communication started with an online journal, Surfaces – the oldest in Canada, now available on the Érudit site – that ran from 1991 until 2001. He is one of the original signatories of the Budapest Open Access Initiative and has been active in the Open Access, Open Science movements ever since. He has served as an expert for the European Commission since 2008, and chaired the Expert Group on the Future of Scholarly Communication and Publishing between 2017 and 2019. He is a member of the Scientific Board of the Nexa Centre for Internet and Society at the Politecnico of Turin and collaborates with various UNESCO initiatives on open science.

All members with one field of their expertise:

- ▶ **Carmen Brando (joined in 2024)**
France, Ecole des hautes études en sciences sociales (EHESS), Natural Language Processing
- ▶ **Paola Galimberti (joined in 2024)**
Italy, University of Milan, Open Science
- ▶ **Elea Giménez Toledo**
Spain, Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)/ENRESSH, Literature and Digital Humanities
- ▶ **Jean-Claude Guédon**
Canada, Université de Montréal (professeur honoraire), Literature
- ▶ **Aliz Horváth (joined in 2024)**
Austria, Central European University in Vienna, East Asian Languages and Civilizations
- ▶ **John Howard**
Ireland, University College Dublin/Coláiste Ollscoile, Baile Átha Cliath, Archaeology, Anthropology, History and Philosophy of Science
- ▶ **Mohamed Khemakhem (joined in 2024)**
France, MandaNetwork, AI and NLP
- ▶ **Mikołaj Leszczuk**
Poland, AGH University of Science and Technology, Telecommunications
- ▶ **Federico Pianzola**
Netherlands, University of Groningen, Literature
- ▶ **Elena Šimukovic**
Lithuania, Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW), Science and Technological Studies
- ▶ **Christof Schöch (joined in 2024)**
Germany, University of Trier, Digital Humanities
- ▶ **Angeliki Tzouganatou (joined in 2024)**
Greece, OpenAIRE AMKE, open and fair knowledge production
- ▶ **Irena Vipave Brvar**
Slovenia, CESSDA, Statistics

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Services and Technology Board

Supervises the service portfolio and associated technologies

The **Services and Technology Board (STB)** is responsible for managing the portfolio of services and associated technologies regarding OPERAS AISBL and OPERAS federated services. This includes all services that are planned, live or to be retired/discontinued. The STB conducts regularly scheduled service reviews. It also collects inputs from other relevant groups or leaders such as EA, GA, OCT, SIGs, SAC, etc. for research community needs and evolution of technology.

Responsibilities include:

- ▶ Advise OPERAS management on the priorities for evolving the service portfolio
- ▶ Conduct regularly scheduled service reviews with service owners
- ▶ Maintain a service strategy and implement the recommendations from the OPERAS GA, EA, OCT and SIGs
- ▶ Steer the creation, review and approval of service design and transition packages, including descriptions and specifications alongside any information to be added to the service portfolio
- ▶ Ensure that major changes to services and solutions are endorsed by the process managers/owners
- ▶ Obtain approval from the relevant governance bodies for all new services and services to be discontinued

The STB holds regular monthly meetings. In 2024, in addition to operational activities, the main focus was on collating usage statistics and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for each of the services as well as analysis of usage behavior for driving the next phase of development.

Board of Governing Representatives

Key governance body of the transition to become an ERIC

The OPERAS Board of Governing Representatives (BGR) plays a key role in shaping OPERAS ERIC, the European Research Infrastructure Consortium. As an independent body separate from OPERAS AISBL, the BGR focuses on critical strategic, legal, governance, and financial matters essential to the ERIC's creation.

Created in November 2023, it held its first meeting early January 2024. Meeting three to four times a year, the BGR works to ensure OPERAS ERIC is built on a sustainable and inclusive foundation, reflecting the interests and commitments of all participating countries. Acting as a precursor to the future ERIC decision-making body, it negotiates and approves the legal framework, governance structure, financial plans, and all founding documents.

Supported by the OPERAS-PLUS project, particularly WP2, WP3, and the OPERAS Coordination Team, the BGR faces the challenge of uniting diverse national interests, timelines and navigating complex international cooperation. Its work is vital in securing OPERAS' future as a leading European research infrastructure.

Special Interest Groups

Bringing the OPERAS community together to develop ideas, exchange expertise, and carry out collaborative research activities

The Special Interest Groups (SIGs) are an important part of the OPERAS engine. Due to their nature, the SIGs are the groups capable of identifying needs and challenges coming from the broader community. Such needs and challenges can then be addressed by OPERAS through projects and the development of new services. Furthermore, the SIGs represent a forum to produce feedback and to assess if OPERAS activities meet the needs of the community.

OPERAS (SIGs) gather experts and promote an international, multi-disciplinary working atmosphere. The groups are open to all members of the OPERAS community.

In 2024, a few changes in the Special Interest Group were implemented. A new SIG on OA Books was created. It gathers the two existing SIGs, Open Access Books Network (OABN) and OA Business Models, that became Working Groups and the new Open Infrastructures for Open Books, already created as a Working Group. The OA Books SIG's main objective is therefore to coordinate meetings and strategic discussions between the three Working Groups. The coordination includes involving the Working Groups in the preparation of agendas for the Policy Forum for OA Books (hosted by Science Europe in coordination with cOAlition S and OAPEN) and in discussions deriving from the Policy Forum meetings.

Open Infrastructure for Open Books Working Group aims at developing and supporting communication channels and engagement between the players in this increasingly complex network, enable increased exchange and interoperability between the different infrastructures, and seed new collaborations, projects and developments, potentially including new OPERAS services, both now and in the future.

The activities of OABN and OA Business Models remain the same, the change was only in the nomenclature of these groups.

The Open Access Books Special Interest Group and its Working Groups show how OPERAS listens to the requests of its community and how the SIGs keep the OPERAS engine moving.

The SIGs continued to use in 2024 a roadmap as a planning tool for detailing yearly activities and aligning objectives with OPERAS' strategies, methods, and ongoing projects.

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Highlights of 2024

Advocacy Special Interest Group

The SIG conducted the Workshop “*Advocacy for Responsible Research Assessment for the Social Sciences and Humanities*” as part of the OPERAS Conference in Zadar, Croatia, on 26 April 2024. As a follow up, the SIG has published a guide on how to reuse the workshop on Zenodo (see: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11669020>) and has created a blog post (see: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/7395>).

Open Access Books Network Working Group

The Working Group started an ‘*Around the World*’ blog series, posting a total of six blogs so far with perspectives on OA books from [Italy](#), [Switzerland](#), [Zimbabwe](#), [India](#), [Colombia](#), and an [introductory post](#). Each of these posts focuses on OA books in a different country and are multilingual: written in the language the person usually works in, with an English translation alongside.

Multilingualism Special Interest Group and OABN Working Group

The Mutual Learning Exercise on Multilingualism aimed at discussing how to put multilingualism into practice. The session comprised two parts. The first one was through the use of the OPERAS service [Mondaecus](#), a collaborative translation platform. The platform was presented and the participants were invited to do a collaborative translation of the [Guidelines on Multilingualism](#), produced in the DIAMAS project. The second part focused on the ongoing blog series [Around the world with the OABN](#).

Tools and Platforms Special Interest Group

During 2024, the group planned to organise a webinar entitled “AI and LLMs as tools for open scholarly communication in social sciences and humanities”, [available on Youtube](#). The aim was to present different initiatives from the OPERAS community related to AI. It included presentations of the LUMEN & GRAPHIA projects, the OPERAS Innovation Lab Accelerator, Open Book Publishers’ experience with AI and some other examples of the use of LLMs in Social Sciences.

OPERAS National Nodes

Empowering and integrating national communities through collaboration and dialogue

The year of 2024 represented a cycle of further structuration and organisation of the OPERAS National Nodes and their communities. With the support of the OPERAS-PLUS project, representatives of the nodes have published another report for their implementation, going deeper into questions, reflections, challenges and opportunities for improvement. The result of this is the deliverable, published in February, **“Mapping opportunities, needs and challenges: OPERAS and the potential national nodes”**, available on Zenodo².

After the finalisation of that report, the work undergone by the nodes started to focus on concrete actions to engage communities, establish partnerships, perform advocacy activities, with the aim of gaining a better structure – including funding – for the national communities. New nodes were kicked-off in 2024, and other nodes performed a series of diverse activities such as dissemination activities for OPERAS services.

During 2024, all the nodes representatives also kept building their relations among them and with the Central Hub via the National Nodes Exchange (which would then be renamed the National Nodes Committee in 2025). These regular encounters helped to answer questions on how to better serve the national communities using the resources that OPERAS federates at the European level, and how to better promote communication and dissemination activities.

In the same pathway, a taskforce was created to produce the first policy brief for the OPERAS National Nodes. Also, the representatives, together with the Central Hub team, worked together to establish a template for the planning of the national node's activities, thus facilitating the process of putting activities forward and also their monitoring.

OPERAS currently has 13 national nodes. In 2024, seven members from national communities joined OPERAS at the European level, further contributing to the network's growth. The basic information of the nodes, together with representative institutions and persons, can be found on the OPERAS website: <https://operas-eu.org/operas-national-nodes/>.

Highlights of the National Nodes in 2024

OPERAS-FI | Finland | Led by TSV (Federation of Finnish Learned Societies)

OPERAS
FI The Finnish National Node is in the process of becoming an active National Node. Throughout 2024, TSV published the CoARA Action Plan to promote responsible assessment, and signed the Barcelona Declaration in support of community-driven policies. Through its two publishing platforms, journal.fi and edition.fi, and its ongoing development, TSV has been contributing to Diamond OA for a long time. In 2025, OPERAS-FI will begin working on outreach activities to promote multilingualism and equitable access to publishing services through communication and dissemination events.

OPERAS-GER | Germany | Led by Max Weber Stiftung

OPERAS
GER Active since October 2020 (with initial funding for 3 years), OPERAS-GER has focused on promoting OPERAS services, fostering community dialogue, and enhancing the visibility of Germany's contributions to Open Science within Europe. Key highlights in 2024 include a workshop in April in Zadar on “How to integrate Library data into GoTriple - a collaboration with the Text+ Consortium”, which showcased the integration of national resources using data from the German National Library (DNB), serving as a model for other libraries.

² Link to the deliverable: <https://zenodo.org/records/10725785>.

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Another milestone was the national meeting of all ESFRI and ERIC infrastructures in September 2024, which provided a strategic opportunity to further strengthen OPERAS-GER's position. In December 2024, the SeDOA consortium was granted funding by the German Funding Agency (DFG) for a three-year term to establish a German single point of contact for Diamond Open Access infrastructures. At the same time, the SeDOA consortium will play an important role in the German National Node of OPERAS with MWS as leading institution. The project will start in spring 2025.

OPERAS-GR | Greece | Led by EKT (National Documentation Centre of Greece)

OPERAS_{GR} Under EKT's leadership, OPERAS-GR plays a strategic role in aligning the Greek SSH research community with the broader European Open Science agenda, particularly through its active coordination of the Special Interest Group "Common Standards and FAIR Principles". By contributing with presentations on services like GoTriple and engaging in collaborations on multilingualism and open access—including promoting outcomes of DIAMAS such as the DOAS in 2024—OPERAS-GR is strengthening the visibility, discoverability, and policy integration of Greek research within Europe.

OPERAS-HR | Croatia | Led by University of Zadar

OPERAS_{HR} Though not yet formally established as a legal entity or funded institutionally, OPERAS-HR was launched on June 16, 2023 and, since then, is actively shaping the country's open access landscape through education, policy advocacy, and community-building activities.

In 2024, OPERAS-HR organised dissemination activities of the OPERAS services, such as the VERA platform, with two events, in May and October, dedicated to the Research for Society service. The OPERAS-HR team has also hosted and organised the OPERAS Conference 2024 which was held in Zadar from 24 to 26 April. Additionally, the node contributes to the scholarly communication landscape by organising the annual PUBMET conference, and in 2024 started the PUBMET Summer School which focuses on scholarly communication in the context of open science. OPERAS-HR also leads the OPERAS Special Interest Group on Best Practices.

OPERAS-IT | Italy | Led by CNR-ILIESI

OPERAS_{IT} The Italian national node of OPERAS operates as a Joint Research Unit (JRU), comprising universities, libraries, scholarly publishers, and representatives from other SSH research infrastructures since 2023. OPERAS-IT has promoted a plethora of activities in 2024, altogether 9 events, including training courses on Open Science topics; presentations of OPERAS and its services, focusing on the VERA platform; and organising events such as the CRAFT-OA tech event, throughout the whole year.

OPERAS-IT fosters close collaboration with other national SSH infrastructures—such as DARIAH-IT, CLARIN-IT, and E-RIHS IT—by concluding joint initiatives under the H2IOSC project (2022-11-01 - 2025-10-31) and pursuing collective funding opportunities.

OPERAS-NL | Netherlands | Led by OAPEN

OPERAS_{NL} OAPEN, as the OPERAS Netherlands National Node, operates both the OAPEN Library and DOAB (Directory of Open Access Books), two globally significant open infrastructures for peer-reviewed OA books. DOAB manages [PRISM](#) which is part of the OPERAS service catalogue.

In 2024, the node team has provided a workshop on the OPERAS Conference, focusing mainly on the work carried out by the PALOMERA project. OAPEN was the scientific coordinator of the project, which researched the OA book policy landscape in the European Research Area providing resources and recommendations for further alignment across the relevant stakeholder groups.

With its longstanding role in supporting academic publishing in SSH, erih+ is currently evolving into a vital actor in Norway's Open Science infrastructure, aligning its goals with those of OPERAS.

Starting in 2024, the Norwegian node started their work with an erih+ seminar in Brussels in September, which included discussions on the OPERAS activities. In December, potential partners of OPERAS-NO gathered in an infrastructure meeting with the intent of integration.

Erih+ is also active in AI-related projects, contributing to OPERAS development in the area of AI. Besides that, the organisation also co-led the OPERAS SIG Tools and Platforms.

OPERAS-PT is contributing with its expertise on Multilingualism through its work as a leader of the Special Interest Group on Multilingualism of OPERAS, and initiated the creation of a new translation service, **Mondaecus**, with the purpose of supporting collaborative work that brings together translators, editors and subject matter experts. In 2024, the platform, in Alpha version, was presented as a potential future service inside the OPERAS service catalogue during the OPERAS Conference, national events in Portugal and online meetings. Mondaecus was also used for collaborative translations in the context of the DIAMAS project.

In 2024, OPERAS-PT organised and hosted a community event at the University of Coimbra to discuss ways of moving forward in relation to open science and open scholarly communication, including the creation of an Open Science community. In the face-to-face event held in May, the team provided a dissemination activity focused on the VERA platform. In September, the node had an online kick-off comprising 12 academic publishers, who are willing to integrate or are already integrated into the national open scholarly communication community.

OPERAS has been included in the Slovenian National Roadmap since 2021, and in 2024 several news and invitations to OPERAS activities were published via the Slovenian Society for Open Science (SSOZ), which greatly increased the visibility of OPERAS; the PALOMERA final conference in Ljubljana (October 2024) also contributed greatly to this.

In May, the first online meeting of OPERAS-SI was held, with a presentation of OPERAS activities and services, with a special focus on GoTriple and VERA. The OPERAS-SI consortium, founded in December 2024, has received funding from the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation for the consortium's activities during the transition period until ERIC is established. The team has been also active in the Slovenian Open Science Community (Slovenska skupnost odprte znanosti, SSOZ).

In 2024 and early 2025, OPERAS-UK carried out a series of activities to increase its visibility and engage key stakeholders in the UK academic and Open Access communities. On 5 December 2024, an online event was held as a "soft launch" to begin promoting OPERAS-

UK and initiate early contacts with stakeholders.

Following the "hard launch" event on 25 February 2025, Jisc established a mailing list for OPERAS-UK members and is planning a programme of engagement in collaboration with the UK community, including webinars, training sessions and information sharing events. OPERAS-UK leader, Jisc, is a member of the OPERAS SIG, Open Access Business Models.

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Beginning with the 2024 Annual Report, we introduce a new feature: a focus on three of the National Nodes, highlighting their work, challenges, and successes over the past year to provide insights and valuable perspectives from the national communities.

Focus on ► OPERAS-ES

In March 2023, the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT) joined OPERAS, simultaneously beginning the design of its activities as OPERAS-ES. This membership, driven by FECYT's role as a provider of public services for the diamond open access academic publishing system, opened the door for Spanish research institutions to join OPERAS as ordinary members. It is worth noting that FECYT operates in alignment with the National Strategy for Open Science (ENCA, in Spanish) and with recent legislative reforms supporting open science, enabling OPERAS-ES to function under the same framework and legal alignment as current Spanish policy.

FECYT's Motivation to Join the OPERAS Infrastructure: Strategic Objectives of OPERAS-ES

FECYT's primary motivation for joining the OPERAS infrastructure was to channel its work as a public service provider in the field of diamond open access academic publishing and to promote the development of an ecosystem based on open access, interoperability, and accessibility of scientific information. OPERAS-ES, as a node within a research infrastructure focused on implementing open science practices in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), which promotes multilingualism in academic communication and supports a knowledge transfer system free of economic and technological barriers, aligns closely with FECYT's operational framework. This alignment allows the Spanish OPERAS node to develop in a coherent and organic manner.

Spain's Role in Advancing Open Access in Europe and FECYT's Contribution

Spain plays a prominent role in advancing open access across Europe, and FECYT contributes significantly to this movement, both through its core activities and its role as OPERAS-ES. By providing training on national and European open science policies, FECYT has supported numerous institutions and professionals, facilitating the transition towards a more open, collaborative, and transparent system. Furthermore, FECYT represents Spain in various international open science forums, promoting knowledge exchange and alignment with European strategies.

In this regard, OPERAS-ES was particularly active in 2024, with a range of national and international activities, including:

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

1. Development of an open science ecosystem through the implementation of the National Strategy for Open Science (ENCA) and the promotion of accessible and sustainable digital infrastructures.
2. Training and capacity building on open science policies at both national and international levels, reaching a wide array of infrastructures and professionals, and facilitating alignment with European guidelines. These efforts included dissemination of the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) and promotion of the Self-Assessment Tool.
3. Participation in European projects where scientific culture plays a central role, contributing tools and resources to improve science communication as an essential element of open science.

Development of Specific OPERAS-ES Activities in 2024

Website Creation

A key first step was the launch of a dedicated website, which serves as a central platform for disseminating information and resources related to OPERAS-ES. This website not only provides access to a wide range of scientific publications and tools but also acts as a virtual meeting point for the open science community. The site was designed with accessibility, usability, and interoperability in mind, ensuring that both researchers and institutions can make full use of its resources.

Mailing List Creation

To support effective and ongoing communication among OPERAS-ES members and other stakeholders, a mailing list was created. This list helps to quickly share news, updates, and opportunities for collaboration, keeping everyone informed about important developments and events within the infrastructure. It also encourages the sharing of ideas and experiences, helping to build stronger community practices around open science. The mailing list currently reaches more than **1,000 professionals** working in academic publishing.

News Dissemination

Disseminating news has been a key task in keeping the community informed about OPERAS-ES activities. Through periodic newsletters, social media posts, and press releases, OPERAS-ES has maintained a steady flow of updated information. This communication strategy has been crucial in increasing the visibility of OPERAS initiatives and attracting new institutions to the cause.

National Node Launch Event in Madrid with CSIC

One of the highlights of the year was the official launch of OPERAS-ES in Madrid, organised in collaboration with the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) in October 2024. The event brought together representatives from a wide range of academic and research institutions, government bodies, and open science experts. It was held in a hybrid format, with around **30 academic professionals attending in person** and a **similar number joining online**. The event provided a platform to present the aims and benefits of OPERAS, encouraging new organisations to get involved and supporting collaboration both within Spain and internationally.

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

Public Presentation of the EDCH

FECYT, in its dual role as a key promoter of open science—supporting, coordinating, and offering services to the scientific community, institutions, and policymakers—and as part of OPERAS-ES, was responsible for organising the public presentation of the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) at its headquarters in Madrid. Although the presentation took place on 15 January 2025, the event had been planned and coordinated throughout the final quarter of 2024. It was held in a hybrid format, with just over **90 people attending in person** and around **200 participants joining online**. The event highlighted the importance of digitising and ensuring access to cultural resources, while also sharing the current progress and ongoing projects in this area. Experts and professionals from the sector took part, offering valuable insights and experiences. The recordings and videos from the session were widely circulated, reaching 130 views in total (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DNGWQzktzZk>)

Promotion of GoTriple

Lastly, OPERAS-ES has actively promoted GoTriple, a multilingual discovery platform designed to enhance access to scientific resources. Initiatives included collaboration with RECYT and the University of Córdoba (UCO) as data providers, ensuring the integration of a wide variety of content and the continuous improvement of the platform. GoTriple has become a valuable tool for researchers worldwide, supporting both multilingualism and open science.

More about OPERAS-ES: <https://calidadrevistas.fecyt.es/proyectos-y-colaboraciones/operas>

FOCUS ON ► OPERAS-FR

The OPERAS-FR national node was launched in 2024. It receives initial support from the COMMONS project, funded under the French Third Programme d'Investissements d'Avenir (PIA3). OPERAS-FR is sustained through institutional in-kind contributions and collaborative European and national projects.

While the core member of OPERAS in France is the CNRS, the National Node is coordinated by OpenEdition, a CNRS research infrastructure dedicated to open scholarly communication in the SSH.

OPERAS-FR communicates through its dedicated [Hypothèses blog](#), [LinkedIn](#), a [Youtube channel](#) and a members' mailing list.

OPERAS-FR plays a key role in disseminating information about OPERAS EU's activities to the French-speaking community, while also promoting the development and national uptake of the OPERAS service catalogue in French. OPERAS-FR ensures that the needs and priorities of the French SSH community are relayed to the European level. It actively supports Diamond Open Access initiatives and works to strengthen the national SSH open science ecosystem by fostering collaboration between institutions, researchers, and a wider audience. OPERAS-FR has been particularly active in 2024, with a wide range of national and international engagements, including:

- **Official Launch of the National Node.**
- **“DOAS en Action” Webinar (Nov 2024):** Presentation of the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) and practical workshop, attended by **60 participants**, following the translation of the standard into French.
- **“GoTriple pour tous” Training Session:** introducing OPERAS services and the GoTriple discovery platform, with practical hands-on training.
- **OPERAS-FR Open Doors Event:** A community-building initiative designed to present OPERAS-FR's activities and invite new stakeholders to engage with the national node.
- **Participation in National Infrastructure Events:**
 - **Journées MEDICIS** in Lyon (June 2024)
 - **Journées SO PUR** at Université de Rennes (Oct 2024)
- **International Collaboration and Visibility:**
 - Participation in the **launch event of the UK OPERAS** National Node
 - Contribution to the **“Carnetiers d'Hypothèses” webinar**, where OPERAS-FR presented the creation of its national website and communication strategy
 - **Participation in the OPERAS Conference 2024** via a poster presentation.
- **Support for Multilingualism** ; Creation of a dedicated translation group to translate into french materials from the DIAMAS project, including the website interface, the toolsuite, and the guidelines.
- **Creation of editorial series on the OPERAS-FR website:**
 - *Plumes Libres* — a guest author series (usually PHD students) offering perspectives on Open Access in SSH
 - *GoTriple pour tous* — a blog series dedicated to exploring GoTriple's features aimed at specific audiences.

More about OPERAS-FR: <https://operasfr.hypotheses.org/>

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

OPERAS

open scholarly communication in the european research area for social sciences and humanities

OPERAS France ; Rich and diverse community supporting open access in the SSH

OPERAS France aims to unite the French OPERAS community and national stakeholders interested in collaboration. It will provide information on projects, news, and events, facilitate dialogue through remote and face-to-face meetings, offer training workshops, share articles on European open access, conduct interviews with European infrastructures, and more.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/operasfr/>

Visit our website!

OPERAS
open access in the european research area through scholarly communication

ERAS est une infrastructure de recherche soutenant la communication scientifique ouverte dans les sciences humaines et sociales en Europe.

POUR LES EDITEURS

Services et outils spécialement conçus pour les éditeurs afin d'améliorer le processus de publication scientifique.

Pathfinder
Rassemble les services d'édition et de communication savante que les membres d'OPERAS proposent à la communauté et donne accès à leur description à partir d'un portail d'accès unique.

PRISM
Permet aux éditeurs d'afficher des informations standardisées sur leurs procédures d'évaluation par les pairs, de les inclure dans les métadonnées des livres, et renforce la confiance dans l'édition en libre accès grâce à une meilleure transparence du processus de qualité.

Metrics
Recueille les mesures d'utilisation et d'impact liées au contenu publié en libre accès à partir de nombreuses sources différentes (monographies, revues, référentiels) et permet leur accès, leur affichage et leur analyse à partir d'un point d'accès unique.

12^{es} journées du réseau Médic
26-28 juin 2024
Lyon

→ Accessibilité numérique

Intelligence artificielle et édition scientifique

Réseau Médici
Métiers de l'édition scientifique publique

DOAS
DIAMOND Open Access Standard

DOAS EN ACTION : COMPRÉHENSION ET PRATIQUE

13 NOVEMBRE 10H - 12H30

PROGRAMME

COMPRENDRE DOAS

- DOAS ET LE PROJET DIAMAS
- DOAS POUR LES ÉDITEURS
- DOAS À L'INTERNATIONAL
- DISCUSSION : DÉFIS ET POSSIBLES SOLUTIONS

ATELIER PRATIQUE

- OUTIL D'AUTOÉVALUATION.
- GUIDE POUR SON UTILISATION

INScrivez-vous !

PIERRE MOUNIER

KARLA AVANÇO

Présentation

GoTriple
PLATEFORME DE DÉCOUVERTE POUR LES SCIENCES HUMAINES ET SOCIALES

Pour les membres d'OPERAS France

Avec la participation de **LUCA DE SANTIS**
Directeur de la recherche chez Net7

10H - 11H
5 JUILLET

INScrivez-vous !

VENEZ DÉCOUVRIR CETTE PREMIÈRE PRÉSENTATION DU SERVICE GOTRIPLE DÉDIÉE AUX UNIVERSITÉS ET AUX ORGANISMES DE RECHERCHE

PRÉSENTÉE PAR

OPERAS
FR

FOCUS ON ► OPERAS-PL

Established in **June 2021**, **OPERAS-PL**, the **Polish National Node led by the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IBL PAN)**, focuses on advancing open scholarly communication within the humanities and social sciences (SSH) in Poland. From the beginning its mission has encompassed supporting open-access publishing models (especially Diamond OA), developing and co-creating digital research infrastructures, and fostering integration between Polish and European SSH communities. Since 2021, OPERAS-PL has also coordinated the **OPERAS Innovation Lab**, dedicated to researching user needs

and developing prototypes of innovative services and tools tailored for the academic environment. The main channel of communication for OPERAS remains the newsletter sent monthly to over 600 subscribers.

In **2022-2024** the node was **funded by the Polish Ministry of Science and Higher Education under the “Science for Society” Programme**. As a part of this project in September 2024, OPERAS-PL actively engaged the academic community through the **“Manifesto of Open Humanities”**. Signed by 200+ individuals and 15+ institutions, the Manifesto by OPERAS-PL calls for systemic support for Open Science in Poland. It advocates for stronger support of non-profit platforms, science policy reform, and sustainable funding for diamond publishers especially in the humanities and social sciences, where open access remains underfunded.

In **2024**, OPERAS-PL marked a significant milestone by **transitioning into a formal consortium on 17 December**. The consortium unites nine prominent Polish institutions, including the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IBL PAN), University of Łódź, University of Silesia, Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC), Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling at the University of Warsaw (ICM UW), Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, National Information Processing Institute (OPI PIB), Centrum Cyfrowe Foundation, and Wrocław University of Science and Technology – CLARIN-PL. The consortium partners prepared an **application for the Polish Road for Research Infrastructures** (finalised in January 2025) with key areas of activity defined as: open scholarly communication, research assessment and scientometrics, innovation management, and internationalisation of Polish SSH outputs.

More about OPERAS-PL: <https://operas.pl/>

OPERAS hosted programmes

Fiscal hosting supporting growth and sustainability

Fiscal hosting (or fiscal sponsorship) refers to the practice of non-profit organisations offering their legal and tax-exempt status to groups—typically projects—engaged in activities related to the sponsoring organisation's mission.

OPERAS proposes a comprehensive fiscal sponsorship framework:

- ▶ Fiscally hosted initiatives become a “program” operated by OPERAS
- ▶ Any work product is available to the public or to the charitable sector.
- ▶ OPERAS as the Fiscal Sponsor
 - ▶ Maintains all legal and fiduciary responsibility for the sponsored initiatives, its employees, and activities but
 - ▶ Delegates the governance to a board elected/appointed by the initiatives founders / funders.
 - ▶ Assures funders that the purposes and any restrictions of all grants and/or contributions will be met.

Open Access Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT)

Community Governed Sharing of Quality, Interoperable, Open Access (OA) Book Usage Data

As part of the OA Book Usage Data Trust's fiscal hosting Memorandum of Understanding, **OPERAS provides essential administrative and infrastructural support, including back-office IT services and accounting.** This support underpins a global initiative dedicated to enhancing the community-governed sharing of high-quality, interoperable, and sensitive data in the field of scholarly communications. Central to this effort is the adaptation of the Dataspace Protocol, which facilitates secure and ethical data sharing management across diverse academic stakeholders.

A key feature of fiscal hosting is leading the Data Trust's legal personality and contractual capacity, enabling it to enter into agreements, receive funding, and formalise partnerships despite not yet being an incorporated entity. OPERAS' fiscal hosting thus plays a foundational role in enabling the OA Book Usage Data Trust to function operationally and to scale responsibly.

The involvement of OPERAS aligns OA Book Usage Data Trust with the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure, which prioritise sustainability, community governance, and transparency. This partnership also enables the transition of essential staff roles from reliance on time-limited grant funding towards a more stable, community-supported model ahead of the official launch of services.

In 2024, the OA Book Usage Data Trust launched a Support Us campaign, encouraging institutions and stakeholders to contribute directly to the development and long-term sustainability of the infrastructure. The campaign reflects growing recognition of the need for transparent, community-led approaches to data stewardship in open-access book publishing.

Moreover, fiscal hosting has facilitated collaborative proposal development with other OPERAS initiatives, fostering stronger cross-project integration and increasing the visibility of the OA Book Usage Data Trust's mission within the broader open scholarly ecosystem.

More about OA Book Usage Data Trust: <https://www.oabookusage.org/>

OBJECTIVE 1. | OBJECTIVE 2.

▶ **European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)** **Serving equitable Open Access publishing in Europe**

The European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) is a collective that provides coordination, tools and services for Diamond OA Publishers, Service Providers, and Tools & Technology Providers. It stands alongside other regional capacity hubs such as Redalyc-Amelica and AJOL, providing a gateway to the global Diamond OA community. Its mission is to build an aligned, sustainable, and high-quality infrastructure that promotes Diamond OA as the standard for scholarly publishing in Europe. **The EDCH is fiscally hosted by OPERAS.**

The European Diamond Capacity Hub first took shape as an idea when the recommendations that came out of the [OA Diamond Journals study](#) were published and called for a capacity-building centre for Diamond OA in Europe. With this vision in mind, the [CRAFT-OA](#) and the [DIAMAS project](#) set out to provide building blocks for what would become the EDCH. Both projects thereby laid the foundation for the federated infrastructure that is the EDCH.

Supported by European institutions (including ANR and CNRS), the EDCH fulfils several key roles:

- ▶ Coordinating and structuring the services of Diamond Capacity Centres (DCCs) across Europe.
- ▶ Implementing and monitoring DIAMAS standards (DOAS) to ensure best practices.
- ▶ Managing a central portal for shared resources and outputs from DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA.
- ▶ Enhancing professionalisation in Diamond OA publishing through training and knowledge exchange.
- ▶ Encouraging the creation of new national DCCs and strengthening existing ones.
- ▶ Representing Europe in the global Diamond OA framework coordinated by UNESCO.

By addressing the needs outlined in the Action Plan for Diamond Open Access, the EDCH ensures a structured, sustainable, and community-driven future for Diamond OA publishing in Europe.

With preparations taking a major step in 2024 through the efforts and outputs of the CRAFT-OA and the DIAMAS project, the EDCH was publicly launched in January 2025. **OPERAS coordinates the EDCH Community Task Force, which supports the Registry and the Forum. Additionally, OPERAS co-leads the Tools and Technology Task Force, which develops technical tools and services to ensure interoperability and compliance across systems.**

Services of the EDCH:

The Diamond Discovery Hub aims to provide an authoritative list of Diamond OA journals in Europe, helping these journals increase their visibility in the academic community and beyond. Diamond OA journals included in the Diamond Discovery Hub must fulfil the six operational criteria for Diamond Open Access.

This is a set of resources that support publishers moving towards Diamond Open Access (OA). They include concise high-level introductions to Diamond OA and to the Diamond OA Standard as well as guidelines and good practices for journal publishing, offering detailed instructions and practical guidance to assist publishers.

The Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) helps foster quality assurance in Diamond OA publishing, providing both a practical guide and benchmarking resources for checking quality and sustainability. It allows Diamond OA Publishers and Providers to assess their compliance with its seven quality components, as well as their financial sustainability.

Publishing Tools refers to a set of software tools, add-ons and other technical developments that serve to improve technical efficiency at the level of publishing workflows and platforms. The publishing tools will also furnish the necessary components to ensure seamless interoperability between various publishing software solutions.

The Registry and Forum are virtual spaces dedicated to fostering collaboration and networking among Diamond OA Community Members. They provide a place where services, tools and technologies can be presented and discussed. All Diamond OA Centers, Publishers, and Providers across Europe are invited to join the Registry to become Community Members.

The Training Platform is dedicated to helping Diamond Publishing Service and Diamond Tools & Technology Providers enhance their skills and build capacity by offering skill-building training modules and curricula in various areas, including the seven components of the Diamond OA Standard.

More about the European Diamond Capacity Hub: <https://diamas.org/>

OPERAS engagement in Europe

Empowering Social Sciences and Humanities research by collaboration

The European Commission has been a strong advocate for Open Science over the years, supporting it both politically—through key strategic documents—and financially, by funding infrastructures and developing the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). A recent milestone is the *Council Conclusions on Research Assessment and Implementation of Open Science*, which recognise Open Access publishing as a foundational pillar of Open Science.

In these Conclusions, OPERAS is specifically acknowledged as one of the key organisations supporting a “European approach and capacities for academic publishing and scholarly communication.” This recognition highlights OPERAS’ critical role in advancing the principles of openness, transparency, and accessibility in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research.

Open Science is not just a scientific imperative but a societal one. By fostering more transparent and inclusive research practices, it becomes a transformative force in addressing global challenges and contributing to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Research today must be co-created with society in an ongoing dialogue, ensuring its relevance and responsiveness to societal needs.

The *Council Conclusions* call for strengthened financial and strategic support for Open Access publishing and open scholarly communication. They advocate for a coordinated approach—both at the policy level by Member States and at the scientific level through collaborations among research organisations. This includes defining priorities, identifying gaps, supporting non-profit Open Access publishers, developing innovative scholarly communication models, and enhancing access and visibility of research outputs. These priorities affirm the need for a dedicated research infrastructure like OPERAS to guide and support this transition.

OPERAS and European Policy on Research Infrastructures

The *Council Conclusions on Research Infrastructures* (2022) emphasise collaboration for scientific advancement, science diplomacy, global challenges, and equitable access to excellence. OPERAS, as part of the Social and Cultural Innovation (SCI) domain defined by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), actively contributes to this vision.

OPERAS has developed strong collaborations with other SSH research infrastructures:

- ▶ **Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs)** were signed with the SSHOC community (May 2022) and CESSDA (September 2022).
- ▶ **Strategic membership** in DARIAH through a dedicated supporting seat in its General Assembly.
- ▶ **Joint participation** in key EU-funded projects: OPERAS-P, TRIPLE, OPERAS-PLUS, SSHOC, and PALOMERA—many of which were initiated by OPERAS to foster collaboration with other ERICs in the SCI domain.
- ▶ **Governance engagement** through participation in the SSHOC Governing Board to align strategies across SSH infrastructures.

OPERAS' Strategic Collaborations in 2024

In 2024, OPERAS expanded its collaborative network across both European and international ecosystems:

- ▶ OPERAS began structured dialogues with **EASSH** (European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities), exploring synergies in policy advocacy and co-shaping research agendas.
- ▶ OPERAS strengthened its engagement with European e-infrastructures such as **EGI** and **OpenAIRE**, working together to integrate open publishing tools and data services into the broader EOSC landscape.
- ▶ Beyond Europe, OPERAS initiated collaborations with **People-Centered Internet**—a US-based foundation committed to ethical, inclusive internet governance—to address **disinformation** and promote trustworthy scholarly communication in the digital age.

These new collaborations reflect OPERAS' commitment to bridge technical, disciplinary, and geographic boundaries, aligning infrastructure development with societal impact.

OPERAS' highlights

- ▶ OPERAS is a member of the **EOSC Association**, actively contributing to the Operational Group of ESFRI-aligned infrastructures.
- ▶ In partnership with **Science Europe**, **Coalition S**, and **ANR**, OPERAS co-authored the **Diamond Open Access Action Plan** and is leading the creation of the **Capacity Centre for Diamond Journals**.
- ▶ OPERAS is among the key organisations recognised in the *Council Conclusions* for advancing academic publishing capacities across Europe.
- ▶ OPERAS is a signatory of the **COARA** Agreement and contributes to its implementation, particularly through its engagement in working groups on:
 - **Multilingualism and language biases** in research assessment
 - **Recognition and reward of peer review** practices

OPERAS is a staunch advocate for **non-profit, equitable, and inclusive Open Access** publishing models. It supports bibliodiversity, promotes multilingualism, and upholds scholarly formats specific to the SSH disciplines, such as monographs and long-form publications. OPERAS also supports the transition to Open Access for academic imprints, working closely with publishers and policymakers to implement sustainable models based on open-source technologies and open standards.

“HIGHLIGHTS the importance of non-profit, scholarly open access publishing models that do not charge fees to authors [...] and NOTES the variety of models that do not depend on article processing charges (APC).”

(Council Conclusions on high-quality, transparent, open, trustworthy and equitable scholarly publishing, p.5)

As one of the main pan-European actors in scholarly communication, OPERAS continues to empower the SSH research community through strategic, inclusive, and cross-sectoral collaboration—shaping a more open and impactful European Research Area.

2. OPERAS as a Service Provider

Service portfolio to support scholarly communication

OPERAS supports the entire cycle of scholarly communication and enables greater community control over openness and accessibility. OPERAS aggregates, federates and scales up resources, providing services to increase the overall quality of SSH research.

Addressing the needs of the research community in SSH, OPERAS empowers researchers with services to discover open scholarly publications and publishing services, improve transparency of peer-review practices, measure usage and impact of open access books, foster research dialogues through blogging, engage in collaborative citizen science projects, and much more!

The *Service Catalogue*³ is the list of services currently offered for the wider research and publishing community, while the *Service Portfolio* is an internal list including not only the services provided by OPERAS to the wider community but also internal services required to operate and coordinate the OPERAS research infrastructure.

There are three types of services provided by OPERAS:

1. **Managed:** Services managed by OPERAS, responsible for overall coordination, delivery and evolution.
2. **Community:** Services managed directly by community providers but discoverable through the OPERAS catalogue. These services are required to have sustainable structures to be established, but receive direct OPERAS participation, contribution and support.
3. **Internal:** Services necessary for managing and operating the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, both technical and non-technical.

OPERAS Service Catalogue

Discovery Services

Exploring Social Sciences and Humanities research in multiple languages

Analytics Services

Measuring usage and impact of Open Access content

Research for Society Services

Activating participatory research in Citizen Science

Quality Assurance Services

Increasing transparency about peer review for monographs

Pathfinder

Finding editorial services for academic publishing

hypotheses

Fostering research dialogues and impact through academic blogging

³ According to FitSM-0 V3, the technical definition is as follows: *The service portfolio is the Internal list that details all the services offered by a service provider, including those in preparation, live and discontinued, while the service catalogue is the customer-facing list of all live services offered along with relevant information about these services. See also: <https://www.fitsm.eu/download/748/?tmstv=1747216264>*

The current service catalogue is provided below:

Managed Services

GoTriple: Facilitates the discovery of millions of multilingual scholarly content from a single access point (publications, authors, projects).

Pathfinder: Enhances the visibility of editorial services and guides editors, editorial managers and authors to discover the best service to fit their needs.

Metrics: Collects usage and impact metrics from various sources related to published Open Access books, which can be accessed, displayed and analysed from a single access point.

VERA: Allows SSH researchers to build citizen science projects together with diverse stakeholders and provides tools to facilitate collaboration and project development.

Community Services

Hypotheses: Provides a space for SSH research blogs, fostering innovative formats of scholarly communication and offering multilingual content.

PRISM: Aims to improve transparency and trust in Open Access book publishing by providing standardised information about the peer-review process.

There are other services in various stages of development that may be included in the OPERAS service catalogue in future. One example is [Mondaecus](#), a platform to provide a collaborative environment for researchers and professionals to translate and edit scientific documents in multiple languages, which received support from the OPERAS-PLUS project for an initial design study and prototype. Similarly, the OPERAS Innovation Lab is planned to be added to the Service Catalogue in 2025 (see section 5).

OPERAS Internal Services

OPERAS ID

Mattermost

Internal services include:

- FitSM⁴:** a training and certification program in lightweight service management mainly for OPERAS members.
- OPERAS ID⁵:** provides a single solution for user registration across all services, offering federated identity such as ORCID, Google, EGI Check-in.
- Messaging⁶:** dedicated Mattermost server for collaborative messaging.

⁴ www.fitsm.eu

⁵ <https://id.OPERAS-eu.org>

⁶ <https://mattermost.com/>

OBJECTIVE 3. | OBJECTIVE 4.

In addition, OPERAS offers a range of services for the OPERAS internal community such as consultancy on FAIR data management and Open Science, IT service management (ITSM), policy development, and coordination in the following areas:

- ▶ Strategy and Policy
- ▶ Legal and Finance
- ▶ Community Management
- ▶ Communication and Outreach
- ▶ Service Management and Technology
- ▶ National Nodes Structuralisation
- ▶ Project Management and Planning

As a legal entity, OPERAS ensures the sustainability and long-term development of its services while aiming to improve the quality and efficiency of scholarly communication in SSH.

2024

At the start of 2022, there were only 4 services in Beta, with 6 services either in the design phase or earlier. By Q4 2024, 8 services were in production, 2 in Beta and 1 in Alpha. The following table provides an overview of the service phase changes for each service.

Service	Q1 2022	Q3 2023	Q1 2025
GoTriple	Beta	Production	Production
Metrics	Beta	Beta	Production
VERA	Design	Beta	Production
Pathfinder	Design	Beta	Beta
Hypotheses	Production	Production	Production
Fiscal Hosting	N/A	Alpha	Beta
PRISM	Beta	Production	Production
Mondaecus	Design	Design	Alpha
FitSM Training	N/A	Production	Production
Messaging	N/A	Production	Production
OPERAS ID	N/A	Beta	Production

Table 2: Service Phase Changes

Future Development

2025 will be a critical year for OPERAS, as the majority of services will be in the production phase. This will require not only a focus on continual service improvement and marketing, but on sustainability as well.

Through the legal entity, OPERAS AISBL ensures the sustainability and long-term development of its activities and services, as well as the effective collaboration and coordination of its members and partners. The AISBL status also enables OPERAS to engage in partnerships and collaborations with other organisations and stakeholders and to represent the interests of the SSH research community at the European and international levels.

However, as OPERAS is transitioning towards becoming a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), current financial and sustainability planning is being defined. Active collaboration is ongoing to ensure that all services are taken into consideration, both current and future. A cost analysis was refined as part of the ESFRI questionnaire update, which is helping to understand total costs and forecasting and is currently being discussed as part of the OPERAS Board of Governing Representatives (BGR).

Finally, OPERAS is participating in a number of EC-funded projects. To ensure organisational, technical and financial sustainability, projects aim to identify Key Exploitable Results (KER) with legal and administrative options that can provide the long-term sustainability of each KER. The OPERAS AISBL and wider RI, is often seen as a potential channel to be explored; however, sometimes sustainability strategies need to be coordinated across a variety of projects and activities. Something that has already been taken advantage of with the GoTriple service as one of the main KERs from the TRIPLE project, where OPERAS serves as the legal host while also supporting the agreement structure. Though it does not necessarily have to be the mechanism that is used, it represents the possibility for KER to be continuously exploited where needed.

▶ 3. OPERAS as a Training Institution

Training Framework & FitSM

An **open science and scholarly communication training framework** is being developed within OPERAS-PLUS. The framework aims to provide the OPERAS community and the Social Sciences and Humanities community at large with a tailored training framework on open science basics, FAIR principle and guidelines to train service users. The kick off of the task took place in 2024 during the OPERAS conference in Zadar. The final version of the framework will be delivered in the summer of 2025.

FitSM continues to remain a strategic component of OPERAS' training framework to ensure high quality service delivery through certification and training initiatives not only internally, but across the academic and research landscape for the ultimate benefit of researchers who consume the services provided.

FitSM is an open source, lightweight standard for professionally managing services. It brings order and traceability to a complex area and provides simple, practical support in getting started with ITSM. FitSM training and certification provide crucial help in delivering services and improving their management. It provides a common conceptual and process model, sets out straightforward and realistic requirements and links them to supporting materials. In addition, participants have an opportunity to receive a formal certification backed by certification authority APMG International for anyone successfully passing the exam.

In 2024, OPERAS organised a FitSM Foundation course co-located with the OPERAS Conference in Zadar, where all 8 participants successfully achieved certification. 2024 also saw an increase in trainings through OPERAS' affiliate and associated trainer network, where an additional 200+ certifications were facilitated.

In 2023, OPERAS became an official Accredited Training Organisation via APMG. In November of 2024, OPERAS successfully passed its first surveillance audit as a quality assurance measure. Moving forward, additional training opportunities will also be provided through projects such as ATRIUM as well as commercially through its network.

FAIR principles

In 2024, the FAIR principles were addressed directly through a variety of ongoing projects, and they will also be part of projects starting after 2024. Within the Skills4EOSC project, OPERAS team contributed a full training for researchers in the SSH that included, among other Open Science's components, an introduction to the FAIR principles. The training was held at the beginning of 2024. As per the project's recommendations, the training material was produced according to a FAIR-by-design methodology ensuring its compliance with the FAIR principles. The experience gained through the use of this methodology allowed the OPERAS team to promote this best practice in another project (ATRIUM).

In the context of CRAFT-OA, the inventory of FAIR-related needs or gaps for Diamond Open Access publishers helped to start designing a FAIR self-assessment tool, whose final delivery is planned for June 2025. Also in 2025, a set of new projects will directly tackle the FAIRification in OPERAS services and beyond. The Horizon Europe projects LUMEN and GRAPHIA, revolving around the improvement and extension of the GoTriple platform, contain tasks dedicated to the FAIRification of GoTriple contents and more generally of SSH research data. This is also the case of the FASCA project, supported by OSCAR Cascading funds, which will focus mostly on the interoperability dimension of the GoTriple data.

Continuing its upskilling activities, OPERAS also organised for the SIG “Standards and FAIR principles” a first presentation of the **FAIR Implementation Profile methodology** in November 2024. The goal was to plan dedicated workshops in 2025 on this methodology historically developed by GoFair. In a second stage, the SIG will discuss the possibility to provide such workshops to the entire OPERAS community.

Finally, beyond the OPERAS strict perimeter, the OPERAS team launched an **RDA Working Group** supported by the RDA TIGER project and called “*Multilingual Controlled Vocabularies in the SSH*”. The Case statement was approved by the RDA Secretary during the summer 2024 and the WG itself was officially launched in September. The objective of the WG is to produce recommendations addressing the specificities of thematic multilingual controlled vocabularies in the SSH. The recommendations should address both scientific aspects (ensure multilingualism quality and multiculturalism equity) and technical aspects (ensure FAIRification of the vocabularies and proper management of these digital objects).

Other Training Efforts of OPERAS

As part of its ongoing commitment to fostering Open Science competencies, OPERAS leads training efforts within the Skills4EOSC and ATRIUM projects, developing targeted courses, workshops and collaborative learning formats to support researchers and research infrastructures across Europe.

OPERAS leads the work package focusing on developing Open Science skills for RIs and thematic communities in the **Skills4EOSC project**. The main objective is to prepare training of trainers (ToT) targeting such communities. In 2024, a training framework designed to help researchers in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) adopt Open Science-compliant practices was produced and tested in a pilot ToT session. The framework is constituted of a learning path with the respective material. This first version is available [online](#) and is accompanied by a [report](#). Based on participants' feedback a new version of the ToT is being prepared to be delivered in 2025. It will comprise four modules focusing on research planning in the Open Science landscape, identify best practices for research data management, explore sharing and publication of research outputs with open science principles in mind, and will conclude with an analysis of the open science research framework from a policy, funding and societal aspect. It will also offer an overview of training design steps.

OPERAS leads the work package dedicated to training within the **ATRIUM project**. The main goal is to build a curriculum where the services offered by the ATRIUM partners are embedded in a broader pedagogical narrative focusing on cross-disciplinary digital methods and wide-ranging competencies in FAIR and Open Science. A survey conducted in 2024 with hundreds of European researchers will help shape the curriculum, so that the courses offered will be based on the identified training needs and skills gaps of researchers. In addition, diverse editions of the workshop formats “Researcher Forum” and “Mutual Learning Exercise” will be organised throughout the project to improve services with the help of end users, in the first one, and bringing together service and data providers, in the second. The first Researcher Forum took place in Poznań, Poland, in October 2024 and focused on the GoTriple platform. The first Mutual Learning Exercise in 2025 will also feature GoTriple.

▶ 4. OPERAS as a Trusted Advisor for Open Science Strategies, including Academic Books

FOCUS ON ▶ Trust/Disinformation

OPERAS has been an active advisor for the topic of Disinformation and how to foster Trust in the Digital Age. The year of 2024 marked the first edition of an international workshop gathering experts to discuss these themes: **TrustOn2024**. The workshop was held in June 2024, at the Royal Library of Belgium, KBR, which co-hosted the event together with OPERAS and Belspo.

TrustOn2024 was organised under the auspices of the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the European Union, aligned with the United Nations' vision of a more trusted digital future, and positioned at the forefront of developing actionable strategies. More than 40 experts gathered around the discussion of Disinformation and Trust, divided into three discussion tracks: Mediation, Science and Infrastructure, reflecting the different perspectives on how to deal with issues faced by contemporary online public spheres.

Besides being a powerful platform to advance solutions and strategies to face disinformation and information disorder, the TrustOn2024 was also a step into the further discussions of the **Science Summit of the 79th United Nations General Assembly (UNGA79)**, held in September 2024. OPERAS hosted an online session during the Summit, providing further insights and deepening the discussions held in June in the KBR. This session **“Fostering Trust in the Digital Sphere: A Multi-Stakeholder Approach Introduction”** explored innovative approaches and strategies to promote trustworthiness in digital interactions through multi-stakeholder collaboration.

OPERAS was also present within *“The Digital Governance Series at the UN Science Summit 2024 - Transforming Science in the Age of AI and Digital Innovation”* with a presentation on VERA in the session: **Defining Digital Citizen Science**, and participating in a discussion on **Science Systems Humanity in the age of AI. Discussion: Responding Perspectives on Equity and Inclusion on Alan Kay's keynote**.

Both of these initiatives dynamised by OPERAS were later

summarised and reflected in a plethora of outputs that were made public in the beginning of 2025. These include a community policy brief⁷, an extensive report containing experts reflections and recommendations from the TrustOn2024 and UNGA79' session entitled "Fostering Trust in the Digital Age"⁸, and an insightful interview with OPERAS co-coordinator Suzanne Dumouchel in the European Science Media Hub⁹.

One highlight on the side of OPERAS footprint for the development of a more trustworthy internet is the **Information Quality Protocol (IQP)**, which is based on the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) developed by the DIAMAS project, and which seeks to be implemented in local and regional scales. OPERAS is eager to contribute to a human-centric internet, providing tools and practices to promote trustworthiness and to fight false narratives and conspiracy theories. Science needs to connect with society, creating a closer connection with people, thus promoting digital and information literacy – and only this way we can have a truly Open Science.

FOCUS ON ► Diamond OA

With the DIAMAS project launching in September of 2022 and the CRAFT-OA project starting in January 2023, OPERAS is participating in two sibling projects dedicated to assess the Diamond OA landscape and foster the development of infrastructure for Diamond OA in Europe. Both projects serve this mission by enhancing the capacity of Diamond OA publishing and providing the building blocks for the European Diamond Capacity Hub. Through outputs such as the *Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)*¹⁰ and policy recommendations, DIAMAS seeks to further establish and coordinate Diamond OA-related efforts and initiatives with a particular focus on the engagement of Diamond OA publishing service providers. Complementarily, CRAFT-OA aims to assess the technical infrastructure in place for Diamond OA and improve it through coordinated efforts.

DIAMAS highlights 2024:

► DOAS & Self-Assessment Tool

The [DOAS](#) is focused on aligning quality and best practices across non-fee-based open access scholarly journals, more commonly known as Diamond OA.

► Diamond OA resources

The [DIAMAS Toolsuite](#) and the [DIAMAS Guidelines](#) explain Diamond OA-related topics and help Diamond OA publishers achieve compliance with the DOAS. A set of resources dedicated to [sustainability](#) aims to support Diamond OA publishers to improve financial sustainability. All of those resources are already implemented into the EDCH service "[Resources & Guidelines](#)"

► DIAMAS Recommendations and Implementation Guidelines for Institutions, Funders, Sponsors, and Donors, and Policymakers

The policy recommendations issued by the DIAMAS project have been developed by a co-design process and are specifically tailored for implementation by Funders, Sponsors, and Donors, Institutional Leaders and Policymakers.

CRAFT-OA highlights 2024:

CRAFT-OA

| EOSC

► PKP Sprint & CRAFT-OA Tech Event

In October 2024 CRAFT-OA hosted two events in Turin: The PKP Sprint, gathered 47 participants from diverse professional backgrounds including journal managers, librarians, user interface experts, and programmers. This

⁷ Available at <https://zenodo.org/records/15047331>. Accessed on 15 May 2024.

⁸ Available at <https://zenodo.org/records/14621383>. Accessed on 15 May 2024.

⁹ Available at <https://sciencemediahub.eu/2025/04/02/fostering-trust-in-the-digital-age-ensuring-the-quality-of-online-information/>. Accessed on 15 May 2024.

¹⁰ The Diamond OA Standard (DOAS) sets out standards for Diamond publishing of scholarly journals in the broadest sense, see: <https://zenodo.org/records/15227981>.

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hands-on workshop focused on enhancing Public Knowledge Project (PKP) open-source publishing platforms, including Open Journal Systems (OJS), Open Monograph Press (OMP), and Open Preprint Systems (OPS).

The CRAFT-OA Tech Event brought together 52 participants from the Diamond Open Access community, institutional publishers, and technical professionals. The two-day gathering featured engaging presentations, hands-on workshops and discussions on innovative technologies shaping the future of Diamond OA publishing.¹¹

► **CRAFT-OA Summer School 2024**

The first CRAFT-OA Summer School for Journal Editors, organised by Masaryk University Press took place in the last week of May at the University Centre in Telč, Czech Republic. The summer school was a unique opportunity to work directly with editors of scholarly journals, who will be one of the main beneficiaries of the project outputs. More than 40 participants from 7 European countries gathered in Telč; the Czech Republic was of course represented, but we also welcomed guests from Poland, Germany, Italy, France, Denmark and Latvia. Speakers from other countries, UK, USA and Ethiopia, participated online.¹²

Joint Highlights 2024:

Throughout 2024, the CRAFT-OA and DIAMAS project have collaborated on a number of webinars. The webinar series “Creating Community-driven Pathways to Equitable Open Scholarly Publishing” was continued with two installments, the second installment focusing on the progress made by the three projects involved (CRAFT-OA, DIAMAS, PALOMERA) and the third focusing on the future impact of the project outcomes.

Additionally, the consortia of CRAFT-OA and DIAMAS conducted the community consultation webinar “Shaping Diamond OA” to define operational criteria for Diamond OA journals.

- 3rd Cross-Project Webinar together with PALOMERA: Creating Community-driven Pathways to Equitable Open Scholarly Publishing - Leading the Way
- 2nd Cross-Project Webinar together with PALOMERA: Where are we now?
- Shaping Diamond OA - Criteria for Journals¹³

¹¹ Learn more about the event: <https://www.craft-oa.eu/author/sona-arasteh/>

¹² Learn more about the event: <https://www.craft-oa.eu/report-summer-school-2024/>

¹³ All of the recordings are available at https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLNSNT11cPt5bx_Pgbn0wbTbew4agcG5Hm

FOCUS ON ► Open Access Books

In 2024, important progress was made toward integrating academic books more fully into national and institutional Open Science policies as one of OPERAS objectives. Two key initiatives in which OPERAS was part of—the **PALOMERA** project and the **Open Access Book Usage Data Trust (OAEBUDT)**—played a central role in supporting policy makers, funders, and institutions with evidence, resources, and governance models that can help shape inclusive and effective Open Access strategies integrating books. These efforts reflect a growing recognition of the need for coordinated, equitable approaches to advance Open Access for academic books across the European Research Area and beyond.

A little over two years ago, the **PALOMERA project** set out to understand why so few open access (OA) funder policies include books, and to provide evidence-based and actionable recommendations to change this. Funded by the European Union and coordinated by OAPEN and OPERAS, it encompassed 16 partners working together to deliver the opportunity for a better Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area (ERA) while developing first of a kind resources for the OA books stakeholders. In October 2024, during an in-person and online conference, the project announced its evidence-based and actionable OA book policy recommendations¹⁴ for fostering robust policy development and assisting policymakers in cultivating a resilient culture of OA book publishing. These recommendations are also expected to benefit other stakeholders such as publishers, researchers, infrastructure providers, libraries, and national policymakers alike. This work was based on two very important

¹⁴ See: <https://zenodo.org/records/14330411>

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outputs of the projects: the [Knowledge Base](#)¹⁵ and [Data Analysis](#)¹⁶. Another goal was to improve the collaboration and communication between the key stakeholders. Through the various events, it raised awareness but also questions on what's next. A very important component of these activities was and still is the Funder Forum representing a collaborative and open forum where funders gathered during the PALOMERA project to discuss OA book policy development within the ERA and beyond. Project partners are now continuing the Funder Forum under the name of Policy Forum for OA Books to better reflect its expanded mission from 2025 onward.

Through Mellon Foundation support, Yannick Legré continued to Co-PI a [three-year effort](#) to develop trusted governance for the sharing of quality, interoperable, **Open Access (OA) book usage data**. With Co-PIs Christina Drummond (University of North Texas) and Prodromos Tsivaos (OpenAIRE), Legré and Ursula Rabar (OAEBUDT Community Manager) collaborated with elected Trustees, project advisors, and subcontractors across five continents. Community norms were identified and documented to support trust and sustainable operations in this neutral data intermediary supporting sensitive and open data transfer management across public and industrial partners. In 2025, resources will be piloted with a [dataspace](#)¹⁷ proof of concept for scholarly communications and Punctum Books, Michigan Publishing, Knowledge Unlatched, JSTOR, Ubiquity with the De Gruyter eBound Foundation, and LibLynx.

Outputs published to the project's [Zenodo community](#) in 2024 include:

- ▶ The first version of a [Participant Rulebook for the OA Book Usage Data Trust - International Data Space \(OAEBUDT-IDS\)](#), alongside the [data](#) and [documentation](#) of the multi-year collaborative process that informed it. The rulebook provided the framework for legal advisors, [Ice Miller LLC](#) to derive standard contractual clauses for pilot participation.
- ▶ Cost recovery workshop [outputs](#) which informed sustainability and membership model development.
- ▶ A [technical gap analysis](#) completed by [67 Bricks](#) which compared existing open infrastructures against International Data Space standards. This report informed the OAEBUDT Board-driven request for proposal process and selection of [Think-IT](#) to lead the technical development of the OAEBUDT dataspace proof of concept.

An OAEBUDT Board approved Supporting Membership pilot program was also launched to explore if organizations would directly contribute to the effort's sustainability.

FOCUS ON ▶ Multilingualism

Multilingualism has been one of OPERAS' central topics since the beginning of the research infrastructure. Holding a Special Interest Group to discuss the political implications and the practical solutions for a more diverse scientific environment, OPERAS members have produced publications, services and projects focusing on the topic.

Besides the now OPERAS Service Candidate – the MONDAECUS platform, featured in the Services section of this Annual Report –, OPERAS has led the **Translations and Open Science Project**, whose aim was to explore the potential role of translation and the associated technologies in the promotion of multilingualism in scholarly communication. In 2024, the reports of the four exploratory studies conducted in 2022-23 were published openly, together with the produced datasets¹⁸. Involving a variety of stakeholders of scholarly communication (researchers, publishers, librarians, translators, publishing platforms, funders, decision-makers, etc.), the exploratory studies were conducted within the following scopes:

¹⁵ See: <https://knowledgebase.oabooks-toolkit.org/communities/d1a1c329-7b66-44ff-b888-c1573a3cac85>

¹⁶ See: <https://zenodo.org/records/14330282>

¹⁷ See: <https://data.europa.eu/en/publications/datastories/when-open-data-meets-data-spaces>

¹⁸ See: <https://zenodo.org/records/10972986>

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- 1) Use-case study for a technology-aided collaborative translation service in open scholarly communication;
- 2) Mapping and collection of scientific bilingual corpora;
- 3) Machine translation evaluation in the context of scholarly communication;
- 4) Operating model for a technology-aided collaborative translation service dedicated to open scholarly communication.

The full reports made available on Zenodo obtained a total of 840 downloads and 5661 views, while the language datasets published on the Ortolang platform were viewed 1750 times and downloaded 73 times, all resources combined. In addition to report and dataset dissemination, the results of the exploratory studies were presented during on-line and on-site events and workshops, including a one-day institutional meeting at the French embassy in Rome, a 90-minute workshop during the OPERAS conference in Zadar, a one-hour webinar held for the European Association of Science Editors (EASE), a joint webinar on multilingualism organised as part of the DIAMAS project, as well as various presentations requested by translation associations particularly in France and Belgium. This interest shown by different expert profiles and stakeholders confirms the relevance of the studies, especially in the age of AI. With their special focus on neural machine translation, the studies addressed before time the technical challenges and the ethical concerns raised by machine-generated content in scholarly communication, which are becoming increasingly crucial with the wide adoption of generative artificial intelligence. Particularly on this point, all the participants to the studies converged towards expressing the need for community-led, transparent, business-independent yet viable technologies, when it comes to multilingual content production, but also AI in general.

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5. OPERAS supporting Innovation

The **OPERAS Innovation Lab**, coordinated by the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IBL PAN), is dedicated to observing and accelerating innovation in SSH scholarly communication. Its mission encompasses designing scalable, sustainable services and promoting cutting-edge solutions for open scholarly communication. The Lab engages with the OPERAS community, broader academic audience, and industry partners to bridge the gap between traditional research methods and emerging digital practices. The Lab is structured around two core functions: the **Observatory**, which monitors and analyses emerging innovation practices, and the **Accelerator**, which offers targeted support to experimental services and partnerships. This dual model enables OPERAS to combine critical reflection with actionable support, positioning the Lab as a long-term coordination mechanism within the infrastructure. At the moment the Lab's team is 5 core members: Maciej Maryl (Chief Researcher), Tomasz Umerle (OPERAS Innovation Manager), Elena Sokolova (Business Development Lead), Magdalena Wnuk (Observatory Lead) and Sy Holsinger (OPERAS Chief Technology Officer) who are supported by several collaborators (see: <https://lab.operas-eu.org/team/>).

In 2024 the OPERAS Innovation Lab advanced its mission to foster innovation in scholarly communication within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) primarily thanks to conducting a case study on selected innovative projects in SSH and using the results to create recommendations for the community of innovators in SSH as well as developing Lab's own vision and agenda for upcoming two years. The year also marked a shift from project-based coordination to a continuous, infrastructure-integrated model of operation, supported by a dedicated internal team and regular workflows.

Here's an overview of the key activities and developments during 2024:

The Lab's website underwent significant updates to better support new projects and the development of the Accelerator program. These updates were part of a broader effort to make the Lab more accessible, transparent, and integrated into the OPERAS ecosystem, allowing it to serve both internal and external communities. Three new subpages introducing Lab's goals and activities were created:

- a) Get involved: <https://lab.operas-eu.org/get-involved/>
- b) Accelerator: <https://lab.operas-eu.org/accelerator/>
- c) Portfolio: <https://lab.operas-eu.org/portfolio/>

The Get involved subpage serves as a direct entry point for individuals, institutions, and initiatives to contribute to the development of OPERAS Innovation Lab. By offering clear pathways to participation, it helps the Lab expand its collaborative network and ensure a diversity of voices in its projects.

Accelerator subpage highlights types of support offered or planned by the Lab in 2025 and 2026. It offers consulting, training, and support in obtaining funding.

The Portfolio at the moment consists of two projects that will be offered pilot support to become one of the OPERAS community services. The JATS XML Converter Service

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stands out as an external service launched in July 2024. The tool automates the creation of XML for full-text articles, enhancing open access publishing. It supports journal editors, academic publishers, and SSH researchers by improving interoperability and machine readability of scholarly content. As of early 2025, 35 journal editors across 22 journals have utilized the service, reflecting its growing adoption.

The blog was enriched with content created as a part of the OPERAS Innovation Lab case study which was published under a separate category: <https://lab.operas-eu.org/category/observatory/innovation-lab-case-study/> in a form of 7 separate blogposts. The thorough analysis of the case study is also available in the 4.1 Deliverable of OPERAS-PLUS published on Zenodo. Apart from these posts the Observatory invited external authors to showcase their work on the website (the call for contributions was published here: <https://lab.operas-eu.org/2024/09/26/operas-innovation-lab-observatory-welcomes-your-contributions/>). As a result 3 blogposts were published: two about innovative tools (JATS XML Converter and Infracfinder) and one about various aspects of evaluating innovation: <https://lab.operas-eu.org/2024/10/04/evaluation-to-foster-innovation-in-ris-in-ssh/>).

In 2025, the Lab plans to launch its first open call for pilot support, finalise its innovation framework, and expand its project pipeline through ongoing collaboration with initiatives such as GRAPHIA and LUMEN. It will also continue hosting Observatory activities, including a new round of case studies and thematic blog series.

Projects Overview

▶ Projects Overview

OPERAS in 2024 maintained a robust portfolio of projects that helped achieve OPERAS vision of making the reality of Open Science and OPERAS mission to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of the Social Sciences and Humanities. Aligned with its four strategic pillars listed below, OPERAS actively led and/or significantly contributed to diverse project activities.

Redesigning Ecosystem

OPERAS-PLUS was instrumental in establishing solid pan-European legal, financial, and governance frameworks, alongside a strategic implementation plan for the European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) formulation. As the project coordinator for **PALOMERA**, OPERAS led the design and co-creation of recommendations for Open Access (OA) book policies in Europe. OPERAS, in **Skills4EOSC**, contributed to the shaping of the science for policy initiatives kit for Competence Centres on Open Science.

Empowering Community

OPERAS engaged with the SSH community through **CRAFT-OA**, **GraspOS**, **OPERAS-PLUS**, **PALOMERA**, **Skills4EOSC**, and **ATRIUM**. These projects drove impact via engagement, outreach, and training initiatives. With a strong focus on exploitation, dissemination, and communication, OPERAS anticipates strengthening community connections.

Supporting Bibliodiversity

DIAMAS aimed to map the Diamond OA publishing landscape across the European Research Area, highlighting its diversity in terms of size, institutional types, locations, disciplines, and languages. The **Translations & Open Science** project actively supported bibliodiversity by addressing the challenge of language diversity in scholarly communication by promoting multilingualism, supporting diverse users, and driving the development of translation technology. Tackling multilingualism positions OPERAS at the forefront of innovation in the SSH.

Fostering Quality

Only through high quality of both provided services and technology supporting them, an efficient, fair, inclusive and sustainable scholarly communication ecosystem for SSH researchers can be achieved. OPERAS, in **OPERAS-PLUS** and **PALOMERA**, built a standard risk management framework, along with rules and procedures to ensure consistent quality of project results. The service management system structure OPERAS established in **CRAFT-OA** upholds the cohesion between products and services being developed across the project. Within **ATRIUM**, OPERAS lays the groundwork for quality research by mitigating the digital gap and assessing researcher skills, competencies, and the needs for training in utilizing its services.

In 2024, OPERAS managed 9 active projects. 7 of these projects – Skills4EOSC, DIAMAS, OPERAS-PLUS, GraspOS, CRAFT-OA, Translations & Open Science, and PALOMERA – continued from previous years. 2 additional projects, ATRIUM and FASCA, commenced in 2024, specifically in January and November.

Beyond these active projects, OPERAS were successful in new proposals: GRAPHIA (led by OPERAS coordination), ALMASI, and LUMEN (with OPERAS contributions). These funded proposals are set to become new projects in the coming year.

Project Profile

For hosted programmes (OAEBUDT, EDCH) and National Nodes Initiatives, please see section 1. (OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient Organisation highly representing the Social Sciences and Humanities OpenScholComm communities of this report.)

HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-01
Sept 2023 - Aug 2025
<https://www.epos-eu.org/skills4eosc>

HORIZON-INFRA-2023-SERV-01-02
Jan 2024 - Dec 2027
<https://atrium-research.eu/>

HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-02
Jan 2023 - Dec 2025
<https://www.craft-oa.eu/>

HORIZON-WIDE- RA-2021-ERA-01
Sept 2023 - Aug 2025
diamasproject.eu/

HORIZON-IN- FRA-2021-DEV-02
Sept 2022 - Aug 2025
operas-eu.org/projects/operas-plus/

HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-01
Nov 2024 - April 2026
<https://oscars-project.eu/projects>

French National Fund
Sept 2022 - Jun 2025
<https://operas-eu.org/projects/past-projects/translations-and-open-science/>

HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-01
Jan 2023 - Dec 2025
graspos.eu

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-42
Jan 2023 - Dec 2024
operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/

Successful Proposals in 2024:

HORIZON-INFRA-2024-TECH-01-01
Jan 2025 - Dec 2027

HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-05
Jan 2025 - Dec 2027

HORIZON-WIDERA-2024-ERA-01
Jan 2025 - Dec 2027

**Connect with the
European research
community!**

Impact

Measuring the Reach and Relevance
of OPERAS across open scholarly
communication communities

Impact

In 2023, OPERAS started to develop a comprehensive **monitoring framework** to evaluate the performance and long-term impact of the Research Infrastructure. This framework provides a structured approach to oversee OPERAS activities and supports strategic decision-making through a set of clearly defined **Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)**. These KPIs are aligned with OPERAS' mission, pillars and current objectives, and they help demonstrate its contribution to society, the economy, innovation, and policy development.

During 2024, OPERAS continued its work on the monitoring framework, a structured data collection, and a way to present visually its performance monitoring and impact. At the **end of August 2025** (as part of the OPERAS-PLUS project), OPERAS will launch a **dedicated online dashboard** offering an accessible, transparent and interactive overview of its monitoring performance and impact across these indicators. This marks an important step in operationalising the monitoring framework and sharing progress with stakeholders and the broader research community.

As part of this framework, the **OPERAS Central Hub** leads efforts in self-assessment, risk monitoring, and quality management. It also offers guidance to National Nodes and Service Providers, using benchmarking and best practices to support continuous improvement across the infrastructure.

In the following, the indicators of 2024 were collected and also compared with those of 2023, demonstrating OPERAS' developing impact.

Pillar: Redesigning Ecosystem

Objective 1. OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the SSH Open scholarly communication communities

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Growth (Size, Outreach)	# New ordinary members (per country, European and non-European)	5 <i>(Cyprus 1, France 2, Spain 1, UK 1)</i>	7 <i>(Denmark 1, France 1, Germany 1, Poland 2, UK 2)</i>	All ordinary members: 52
	# New core members	3 <i>(Spain, Finland, Norway)</i>	0	All core members: 13
	# New supporting members	1 <i>(France)</i>	0	All supporting members: 4
	# Private organisations within OPERAS members	5	5	5

Public awareness & Outreach¹⁹	# Visits on the OPERAS website	27,811	38,320 (increase of 37,8%)	
	# Followers on OPERAS Social media channels	4,533	5,515 (increase of 21,66 %)	
	# Social Media posts on all OPERAS social media channels	587	903 (increase of 53,84%)	
	# Publications on Zenodo	133	78	436
	# Other Publications	1	2	
	# Events of OPERAS (counting training as separate)	47	45	
	# Project related events	126	105	
	# People reached and engaged in OPERAS events	1294	839	
	# People reached and engaged in project related events	6000	7140	
	# Hours of OPERAS events	53	70	
Collaborations/ Building a European Network	Qualitative Use case: collaboration in a long-term perspective	Long-term evaluation to be conducted once collaboration completes minimum 10 years.		
Service Providers	# Members in the Services and Technologies Board	8 organisations	10 organisations (24 persons)	
	# Agreements with Service Providers	1	4	4
	# Private organisations/ SMEs providing service components for OPERAS	4	5	

¹⁹ Most indicators are measured without taking into account the project activities of which OPERAS is a part, unless this is clearly indicated. The 2023 data has been updated accordingly.

Financial and Economic	FTE (full-time-equivalent) employees (AISBL)	10.8 FTE	12.9 FTE	
	# country of work/ number of nationalities of OPERAS AISBL staff	8 countries <i>(Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Switzerland)</i>	8 countries <i>(Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Switzerland)</i>	
		11 Nationalities <i>(Belarusian, Belgian, Brazilian, Croatian, French, German, Greek, Italian, Portuguese, Taiwanese, US-American)</i>	12 Nationalities <i>(Belarusian, Belgian, Brazilian, Croatian, French, German, Greek, Italian, Portuguese, Russian, Taiwanese, US-American)</i>	
	# Number of new jobs at each level - senior and junior (AISBL)	5 senior	2 senior	
	Case study: Diversity of people and professional background (examples)	Case Study: Leveraging Diversity for a Stronger European Research Infrastructure: The Case of the OPERAS coordination team, <i>(see below this table)</i>		

CASE STUDY: Leveraging Diversity for a Stronger European Research Infrastructure: The Case of the OPERAS coordination team

OPERAS, a key European research infrastructure (RI) for open scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities, stands as a model for diversity and inclusivity. This is reflected not only in its ability to bring together various stakeholders, members, and research communities in open scholarly communication within the social sciences and humanities (SSH) and beyond, but also in the OPERAS Coordination Team (OCT), which includes OPERAS AISBL staff.

As in our Code of Conduct²⁰, “We support diversity in all dimensions.” This principle applies to every activity we undertake. The tangible impact of the diverse composition of the OPERAS coordination team in its operational effectiveness, stakeholder engagement, and capacity to develop and deliver innovative solutions.

²⁰ See the code of conduct, <https://operas-eu.org/about/governance-schema/coordination-team/how-we-work/>

The OPERAS coordination team is the central hub of OPERAS comprising by the end of 2024 of 20 persons: 14 hired by OPERAS AISBL and 6 persons working for 4 different (core) members of OPERAS (OpenEdition - France, University of Coimbra - Portugal, Max Weber Stiftung - Germany, University of Zadar - Croatia). This collaboration of OPERAS AISBL staff and staff from OPERAS member institutions demonstrates our distributed approach in community management. OPERAS is committed to diversity of interpretation and believes that many ways can lead to our common goal.

Within the OPERAS coordination team, individuals from a wide range of nationalities, cultural, linguistic, disciplinary and professional backgrounds can be found. Specifically in 2024, the team:

- ▶ consists of people from **Asia (1), Europe (16), North America(1)** and **South America (3)** creating a dynamic and intercultural environment.
- ▶ average age range **26 - 35** = 5%; **36 - 45** = 55%; **46 - 55** = 35%
- ▶ Gender: **Female 66,67%, Male 33,33%**
- ▶ Has a professional background, that ranges from industry (business, film, marketing) to scholarly based professions including those related to research, library work and publishing.
- ▶ **12 Nationalities** (Belarusian, Belgian, Brazilian, Croatian, French, German, Greek, Italian, Portuguese, Russian, Taiwanese, US-American)
- ▶ **57,14 %** of the staff work from another country than their first nationality, working in **10** countries.

The variety of personal and professional backgrounds in the OPERAS coordination team leads to:

▶ **A centre of various competencies:**

Cloud of competencies from the OPERAS coordination team, December 2024

- ▶ **Enhanced multicultural collaboration:**
The diversity of nationalities and cultural perspectives has led to the adoption of best practices in intercultural communication and project management, fostering collaboration across borders and disciplines.
- ▶ **Innovation and idea hub through diverse perspectives:**
The interplay of different professional and academic backgrounds and experiences enhances creativity and problem-solving, leading to innovative approaches to open scholarly communication in SSH.

► **Alignment with European Commission priorities:**

OPERAS AISBL's diversity directly supports European values and policy priorities, including the European Research Area's emphasis on gender equality, diversity, and inclusiveness in research. It also contributes to the European Commission's goals for international cooperation in research and innovation.

An intercultural environment strengthens team competencies but also requires continuous training. A dedicated training on intercultural communication and organisation in December 2024 supported the capacity-building and will lead to further organisational structure changes in 2025 within the OPERAS coordination team.

Beyond the OPERAS coordination team, the research infrastructure is also further strengthening diversity in its governance to better reflect the full spectrum of the SSH community. This is already visible in the composition of OPERAS' governance bodies.

With a team composed of individuals from different backgrounds, professions and perspectives, OPERAS is better positioned to meet the needs of Europe's diverse research communities and to foster a more inclusive, innovative, and impactful European Research Area.

Pillar: Supporting bibliodiversity

Objective 2. The Diamond model supported as a major one in the scholarly communication ecosystem

Area	Indicator	2024*
Community Building	# Institutional publishers using the European Diamond Capacity Hub	
Capacity Hub	# Number of training events offered by European Diamond Capacity Hub	
	# Diamond journals in the Diamond Discovery Hub database	

**Given the recent launch of the European Diamond Capacity Hub in January 2025, it is currently not possible to track or report the previously mentioned indicators within this annual report. Data collection for these indicators will start during 2025 and will be presented in future reports. Likewise, the Diamond Discovery Hub database, which is being developed within the CRAFT-OA project, will only be launched in June 2025, meaning those indicators are also not yet available. Nevertheless, the early impact of these initiatives is already visible: Diamond is playing a major role within national communities, with several countries, including Finland, Norway, Sweden, Germany, and Italy, actively preparing to set up their own national Diamond Hubs. This highlights the growing momentum and relevance of Diamond initiatives across Europe.*

Pillar: Empowering Community

Objective 3. OPERAS services published and integrated with EOSC and other marketplaces and communities

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Uptake of OPERAS services ²¹	# Visits of each OPERAS managed service	GoTriple 15,425	GoTriple 192,700 VERA 1,886 Metrics 240 Pathfinder 653 ²²	
	# Top 3 European countries in which the services are most used	GoTriple Italy, Germany, France	GoTriple Germany, France, UK VERA France, Italy, UK Metrics UK, Spain, Germany Pathfinder Italy, France, UK	

OPERAS has 6 services in the service catalogue and 9 in the service portfolio. (Status May 2025)

- ▶ **GoTriple**, a discovery platform for Social Sciences and Humanities in multiple languages, provides access to over **17,5 million documents by the end of 2024 from more than 1,400 data sources (an increase of 2,5 million documents compared to the previous year)**.
- ▶ **Hypotheses**, a dedicated service fostering research dialogues and impact through academic blogging, draws approximately **1 million unique visitors** per month, hosts around **5,000 active blogs**, and engages almost **22,000 active accounts (around 2,000 more accounts than in the previous year)**.
- ▶ **VERA**, activating participatory research in Citizen Science, supports **more than 100 projects**.
- ▶ **PRISM**, a tool for increasing transparency about peer review processes for monographs, hosts **approximately 6,000 titles and connects 20 publishers**.
- ▶ **Pathfinder**, a service aimed at finding editorial services for academic publishing, collaborates with **7 service providers (3 more than in the previous year)** to offer **34 options (7 more than in the previous year)**.
- ▶ **Metrics**, a service measuring usage and impact of Open Access content, engages with **82 publishers (33 more than in the previous year)** and about **8,300 books tracked (5,000 more than in the previous year)**, complemented by the installation of around **40 widgets** to enhance user interaction and accessibility.
- ▶ Significant progress includes the operationalisation of the **OPERAS ID (1,148 registered users by the end of 2024)**, which simplifies user access across all OPERAS services and currently integrates Google, ORCID and EGI Check-in, others in the development pipeline, and the **FitSM training** that enhances service management capabilities within the community.

These developments underscore OPERAS' commitment to fostering an integrated and efficient research infrastructure.

²¹ The OPERAS services VERA, Metrics and Pathfinder were in Beta version in 2023, therefore no data is available for that year.

²² Data collected only from March 2024.

Pillar: Fostering quality

Objective 4. Clear set of well-defined and operational services

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Services	# OPERAS Services in the Services Portfolio	9	9	9
	# OPERAS Services in Evaluation		2	
Business models for Services	% Availability/ Reliability of the service	<i>This indicator can only be measured in the future to assess the capability.</i>		
	% Services with a clear defined business model	<i>Further evaluation is required for this indicator as all the services are self-funded currently.</i>		
FitSM	# Personal Certifications		57 directly (facilitated 300+ through our facilitated trainer network) ²³	
	Use case: services and the clear-defined business models	<i>Further evaluation is required for this indicator as all the services are self-funded currently.</i>		
	Case study: Quality of the OPERAS services	Case study: Elaborating the quality of OPERAS services: GoTriple and the ATRIUM Researcher Forum (see below this table)		

CASE STUDY: Assessing the quality of OPERAS services: GoTriple and the ATRIUM Researcher Forum

One of the ways in which a Research Infrastructure can measure and improve the quality of its services is a Researcher Forum. In this context, the OPERAS discovery service *GoTriple* was the target of one of these events, organised by the ATRIUM project (Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities). The ATRIUM Researcher Forum on *GoTriple* was realised in October 2024 and its main goal was to gather feedback from users and experts about *GoTriple* to identify the platform's strengths and areas for improvement.

Twelve researchers from Poland took part in the event, divided into two groups: new users and experts. The new users group participated in a usability test in which they performed tasks on the *GoTriple* platform while verbalising their thoughts and challenges encountered. They also participated in a follow-up group discussion about their experience with the platform during the test. The experts group engaged in a focus group to evaluate key features of *GoTriple* and in a panel to discuss potential development directions for the platform.

Together, the organiser of the event and the *GoTriple* team identified some key results, both in the platform strengths and challenges. Among the strengths, the platform was found to be intuitive, user-

²³ Thanks to the OPERAS training initiatives and the resources accredited by APMG.

friendly with an easy navigation, having useful filtering and knowledge maps/streamgraphs, and a promising chatbot. Challenges include limitation of literature representation in given areas, needing better integration with external tools, an improvement of the search in languages other than English and a potential to expand extra tools.

The first Researcher Forum will be followed by a second one, to be realised in 2025. And the results are already being put into practice, with the GoTriple team using the feedback to improve the platform continuously, and leveraging the lessons learned also in following projects such as FASCA, GRAPHIA and LUMEN.

Read more about it: <https://atrium-research.eu/news/atrium-first-researcher-forum/>

Pillar: Empowering community

Objective 5. OPERAS members and communities are trained and knowledgeable in SSH FAIR and Open Science practices

Area	Indicator	2023 ²⁴	2024	In total since 2024
Training	# Training events of OPERAS National Nodes		2 (Italy) 1 (Croatia)	3
	# Participants attending training events		110	110
	Use case: Uptake of FAIR principles	<i>Data collection for this indicator is currently not feasible and requires further evaluation</i>		

Pillar: Fostering Quality

Objective 6. OPERAS members are trained and knowledgeable in SSH open science service delivery

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Service delivery	# Training events (FitSM)	6	1	7
	# Training participants (FitSM)	37	8	45

²⁴ The data of the National Nodes have been collected since 2024, as a result of the Roadmap for the OPERAS National Nodes.

Pillar: Redesigning Ecosystem

Objective: 7. OPERAS as a trusted advisor for national and European OS strategies

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Scientific advisor and engagement with policymakers	Case study: Example of consultation	Case study: The PALOMERA validation process (see below this table)		
	# Policy briefs		1	1
	Case study: Notable changes in policy decisions	<i>The impact of OPERAS activities on notable changes in policy decisions cannot be validated enough at the moment. But it is under constant evaluation and will be conducted within the next 2-3 years.</i>		
	Case study: OPERAS impactful publications	<i>See Key Publications of 2024 in the appendix 2 of this annual report</i>		
Engagement with key initiatives	# & Case study: Boards and task forces of which OPERAS is a member	5 (CoARA, EOSC, RDA working group, SSHOC, OAEBUDT)	7 (CoARA, EASSH, EDCH, EOSC, RDA working group, SSHOC, OAEBUDT)	7
		Case study: OPERAS already conducted a “USE CASE: Boards and task forces of which OPERAS is a member” for the annual report 2023, see: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11349719 (page 67) .		

CASE STUDY: The PALOMERA validation process

The PALOMERA (Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area) project, of which OPERAS is a coordinator, demonstrates a sophisticated approach to stakeholder consultation through its structured validation exercises. As documented in Deliverable 5.3²⁵, these exercises represent a methodical process for ensuring that key project outputs receive proper assessment from diverse stakeholders across the European Research Area.

PALOMERA distinguished validation from other engagement activities by focusing on obtaining collective assessment from stakeholders regarding the validity of project outputs. The project implemented three distinct validation exercises, each tailored to a specific Key Exploitable Result (KER):

- ▶ Knowledge Base Validation (January 2024): This two-part exercise involved 34 participants representing 17 countries and all relevant stakeholder types (RFOs, RPOs, researchers, policymakers, publishers, libraries). The process included initial presentation, feedback collection via Google Forms, and focused breakout discussions to assess the completeness of the Knowledge Base and explore potential use cases.
- ▶ Analysis Validation (June 2024): Taking the form of scholarly peer review, this in-person exercise brought together three expert reviewers from different geographical locations (US, UK, France) with diverse backgrounds to evaluate the analysis of OA book policies using the PESTLE framework.

²⁵ Available in: <https://zenodo.org/records/14265343>. Last accessed on May 28, 2025.

- Recommendations Validation (September 2024): This five-step process included initial feedback gathering, presentation of draft recommendations, structured feedback collection, breakout discussions by stakeholder type, and final refinement. The exercise engaged 28 participants from 14 countries.

The validation exercises deliberately involved all stakeholder types identified in the project's Grant Agreement, including research funders, research institutions, researchers, policymakers, publishers, and libraries. This comprehensive approach ensured that the project's outputs would be judged valid by those who would ultimately implement or be affected by OA book policies.

This case from the PALOMERA project illustrates how structured validation exercises can serve as an effective consultation mechanism within research infrastructure projects. Co-coordinated by OPERAS, the project is an example of how the infrastructure positions itself as an advisor for Open Science and Open Scholarly Communication.

Pillar: Supporting Bibliodiversity

Objective 8. Academic books are included in the Open Science policies

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
A set of recommendations and resources provided to support institutional strategies and funder policies for open access books	# Recommendations		43 (single recommendations)	
	Case study: Examples on how recommendations are used	Case study: OPERAS already conducted a "USE CASE: How recommendations are used?" for the annual report 2023, see on page 66: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11349719 .		

Pillar: Empowering Community

Objective 9. Setting up a pan-European OPERAS innovation lab

Area	Indicator	2023	2024	In total
Innovation	# of calls run through the innovation lab	0	2	2
	# of blog posts on the observatory	6	9	15
	# of new services proposed to the OPERAS service portfolio	0	1	1
	# of new pilot proposals submitted	0	3	3
	# of case studies + case study	0	4	4
Case study: All case studies of the innovation lab can be found here: https://lab.operas-eu.org/category/observatory/innovation-lab-case-study/ .				

Appendix

Appendix 1: Financial Report

The financial statement is presented as of 31 December 2024, verified by OPERAS' statutory auditor, who delivered unqualified opinion to the annual account for the year 2024.

The end-of-year accounts show a positive result amounting to 68,329 €, which accumulated to the previous end-of-year totals 381,649 €.

Table of OPERAS Financial statement 2024

Income and Expense Account	€ BAL 2024
Projects incomes	1,361,530
Membership fees	150,000
Subsidiaries FR	94,607
Other funding	26,176
TOTAL INCOMES	1,632,314
Subtotal employee costs	-1,252,632
Subtotal office costs	-162,146
Subtotal financial and professional costs	-71,097
Subtotal project costs	-90,822
TOTAL EXPENDITURES	-1,576,697
Profit end-of-year 2024	55,617
Financial revenue	29,138
Financial charges & income tax	-16,425
Net results	68,329
Brought forward end-of-year	313,319
Cumulative profit (equity)	381,648

- 83%** ▶ **Project incomes**
- 9%** ▶ **Membership fees**
- 6%** ▶ **Subsidiaries FR**
- 2%** ▶ **Other funding**

OPERAS AISBL Equity 2020 to 2024 in €

Number of Members of OPERAS participating in projects in 2024

The funding projections for members in 2024 are expected to be linear compared to 2023. There is a gap of 232,000 euros due to the TRIPLE project ending in 2023. However, we anticipate new income from two new projects, ATRIUM and FASCA, which will generate an estimated linear funding of 581,000 euros. Overall, the increase in project revenue amounts to 12%.

Projects	Number of project partners	OPERAS Members	Number of OPERAS Members	SUM of Funding in 2024
ATRIUM	28	Core members	1	47,850.00€
		Ordinary members	2	97,000.00€
		Supporting members	1	419,453.13€
ATRIUM Total			4	564,303.13€
CRAFT-OA	23	Core members	7	€310,854
		Ordinary members	5	€161,438
		Supporting members	1	€245,375
CRAFT-OA Total			13	€717,667
DIAMAS	22	Core members	7	€230,512
		Ordinary members	5	€226,258
		Supporting members	1	€11,458
DIAMAS Total			13	€468,229

FASCA	5	Core members	1	€5,500
		Ordinary members	2	€11,124
FASCA Total			3	€16,624
GraspOS	18	Core members	1	€41,875
		Ordinary members	1	€108,333
GraspOS Total			2	€150,208
OPERAS-PLUS	14	Core members	10	€462,965
		Ordinary members	3	€70,252
		Supporting members	1	€15,500
OPERAS-PLUS Total			14	€548,717
PALOMERA	16	Core members	5	€349,375
		Ordinary members	3	€56,625
		Supporting members	2	€157,063
PALOMERA Total			10	€563,063
Skills4EOSC	43	Core members	2	€79,469
		Ordinary members	3	€127,570
Skills4EOSC Total			5	€207,039
Grand Total				€3,235,849.75

OPERAS AISBL project resource used in 2024 and funding claimable

Projects	Used PM in 2024	SUM of Funding in 2024
ATRIUM	5.8	€55,577
CRAFT-OA	14.9	€182,570
DIAMAS	15.4	€120,067
FASCA	0.3	€3,300
FNSO-MESR	7.8	€82,870
GraspOS	11.6	€122,717
OAEBUDT	7.4	€94,667
OPERAS-PLUS	34.5	€481,643
PALOMERA	12.8	€170,444
Skills4EOSC	17.2	€131,456
Grand Total	127.7	€1,445,311

Appendix 2: Publications

Publications and reports from the OPERAS community

Focus on Key Publications

Exploratory studies for the creation of a technology-aided collaborative translation service in open scholarly communication - Susanna Fiorini

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10972986>

4883 views | 288 downloads

Since the Helsinki Initiative in 2019, language diversity and multilingualism have become key concerns in scholarly communication. Among the initiatives working towards a sustainable multilingual science, the Translations and Open Science project explores the potential of technology-aided translation to help produce and disseminate research in multiple languages.

This report presents an overview of the four exploratory studies conducted as part of the Translations and Open Science project in order to lay the foundations of a technology-aided collaborative translation service for open scholarly communication. More detailed information can be found in the specific deliverables of each study, cited as references in the report.

PALOMERA Deliverable 4.2 - The PALOMERA Recommendations for Open Access Books - Bandura- Morgan, Laura; et al.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14049032>

2540 views | 984 downloads

The PALOMERA project set out to understand the policy landscape of OA books and the challenges preventing research funders and institutions in particular from including books in their OA policies. One of the project's main goals was to support the key stakeholders in the field by providing evidence-based, aligned, and actionable recommendations that can help formulate OA book policies.

Open Access books are defined here as scholarly, peer-reviewed books including monographs, book chapters, edited collections, critical editions, and other long-form scholarly works. Textbooks and popular science books are seen as a different category, although the policy recommendations could potentially be extended to this category of books as well when they are published Open Access. Open textbooks are deliberately left out from this definition because they require a different process: policies regarding open textbooks must take into account considerations about Open Educational Resources, which are beyond the remit of the PALOMERA project.

In Deliverable 4.2, PALOMERA has developed an extensive set of actionable and aligned recommendations on Open Access (OA) books for eight stakeholders: (1) Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and research institutes, (2) Public and private Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), (3) National policymakers, (4) Academic and national libraries, (5) Researchers, (6) Learned societies, (7) Infrastructure providers, and (8) Academic publishers. These stakeholders are uniquely positioned to drive a transition to OA books by embedding OA principles for books into their policies and strategies. Since the current landscape of OA book policies is characterised by a lack of policy alignment between various relevant stakeholders, this change requires an aligned effort based on policy recommendations for various stakeholders that are grounded in solid evidence.

The evidence for these recommendations has been provided by the Knowledge Base developed in WP2, which contains over 650 open access policy and related documents and a set of 40 stakeholder interviews, as well as on the research undertaken in WP3 which provides a unique overview of the OA books policy landscape in Europe. For each set of recommendations, we have defined a timeline by prioritising recommendations in terms of short term (1-2 years), medium term (3 years), and long term (4-5 years) time frames.

The project has performed three validation exercises to check the validity of 1) the data collection and methodology; 2) the analytical approach, methodology, and key findings; and 3) the recommendations themselves. This approach was chosen to increase the engagement with all relevant stakeholders and to strengthen the outcomes of PALOMERA.

The recommendations integrate the valuable comments of two reviewers, as well as the constructive comments from the subgroup on scholarly communication of the European University Association's (EUA) Expert Group on Open Science and the LIBER Working Group on Open Access.

Report on the PALOMERA survey on open access policies for books in the European research area - Dreyer, Malte, et al.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14329142>

2048 views | 1019 downloads

As part of the data collection for the project 'Policy Alignment for Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area' (PALOMERA), a survey was designed and distributed on the needs, obstacles and challenges of policy-making for open access books. It was directed at various stakeholder groups and aimed to identify attitudes and levels of knowledge about open access book policies in general and individual measures in particular. The report provides the result and overview of the survey with the questionnaire divided into six sections: 1) General information about the respondents; 2) Awareness of open access policy measures; 3) Stakeholders and players; 4) Attitudes towards the design of policies for open access for books; 5) Attitudes and policy measures for open access books; and 6) Policy measures.

OPERAS CoARA Action Plan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14267997>

247 views | 363 downloads

In 2022, OPERAS joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) to support research assessment reform. This action plan outlines OPERAS' strategies to implement these reforms through various activities and services focused on the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). In this page we summarise the OPERAS Activities in relation to research assessment reform in 2023-2024; and the directions for the Action Plan.

EDITORS: Fotis Mystakopoulos & Jadranka Stojanovski

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